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AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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Report on best practices on refugee and migrant children

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Summary

The present report summarizes the comprehensive set of positive, innovative, and effective good practices and resources for the socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children which are included in the Online Digital Database, and presents the strategies to promote their replicability and advancement among target users and stakeholders.

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Report on best practices on refugee and migrant children

1 Executive summary

The present report is the outcome of the IMMERSE task T5.4 “Online digital database of good practices and resources in social integration of refugee and migrant children”, included in the Work Package 5 “Social awareness and stakeholder engagement”.

The report analyses and summarises the comprehensive set of positive, innovative, and effective good practices and resources for the socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children which are available at the Online Digital Database (deliverable D5.3).

The database is aimed at helping school leaders, teachers, educators and social professionals to identify supportive environments, educational conditions and practical resources relevant for the social integration of migrant children.

The report on good practices and resources includes:

- A summary of the identification requirements followed by the research partners to select the good practices and resources
- An analysis and graphical representation of the good practices and resources included in the database, on the basis of the main research criteria followed by the research partners for each category
- The last section presents the complementary set of strategies to be implemented by IMMERSE partners to promote the replicability and advancement of good practices and resources among target users and stakeholders
- The title and description of all the good practices and resources included in the database is available in the annexes

2 Selection of good practices and resources

The present report is the outcome of the IMMERSE task T5.4 “Online digital database of good practices and resources in social integration of refugee and migrant children”. The database has been designed and developed as a digital practical tool aimed at helping school leaders, teachers, educators and social professionals to identify supportive environments, educational conditions and practical resources relevant for the social integration of migrant children. The database provides them with an exhaustive compilation of 109 good practices, projects, policies, methodologies, pedagogical approaches, resources and tools in socio-educational integration of migrant children.

The database is freely accessible at the project site in English, Spanish, Italian, French, Dutch, German and Greek. <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/online-digital-database-of-good-practices-and-resources-in-social-integration-of-refugee-and-migrant-children/>

The good practices and resources included in the database have been selected through two processes on the basis of the following categories:

Good Practices – 60 resources

- Good Practices in educational and social integration of refugee and migrant children, identified in the framework of the task T4.2 “Best practices on refugee and migrant children integration”

Policy Papers – 24 resources

- Guidelines, recommendations, legal regulations, regional, national or international plans, public strategies, publications from forums or conferences, related with the field of IMMERSE project

Other tools and resources – 25 resources

- Other tools and resources related to the field of IMMERSE project: videos, audios, text documents, online libraries, sites, awareness campaigns, toolbox of activities, etc.

In the framework of Work Package 4, task T4.2 “Best practices on refugee and migrant children integration”, IMMERSE research partners collected 60 good practices across several European countries, which were evaluated through a comparative analysis.

The methodology to collect and analyse these good practices is explained in detail in the deliverable D4.1 “Collection of good practices”. As a summary, the following identification requirements for a good practice were taken into account:

Efficacy	Efficiency
The capacity to achieve the objectives as	The adequate use of resources to achieve the set

<p>attested by rigorous validation and evaluation of the results.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Correspondence between the practices' purposes and the outcomes identified in the IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators. ▪ Potential to increase the social capital and foster the empowerment of stakeholders and targets (e.g., access to networks and communities; commitment to the community's well-being). 	<p>objectives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Means-ends consistency. ▪ Internal organization and reflexivity (professional resources, disposition to learning by doing, team working, etc.). ▪ Partnerships activated and characters of the overall governance (e.g., participation and inclusiveness of stakeholders).
<p>Reproducibility and Transferability</p>	<p>Political relevance</p>
<p>The potential of interventions to be replicated in similar and/or different contexts, respectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Availability of communication tools to promote the effective transfer of experiences and methodologies. ▪ Identification of paths and processes necessary for transferability (e.g., human resources, training, structures and equipment, costs, etc.). ▪ Identification of the risks and mitigation possibilities in transferring the practice to disadvantaged contexts with less economic, social, and cultural capital. ▪ Possibility of an ex-post evaluation of the transfers made. 	<p>The ability of projects to contribute to the implementation of national action plans and be in line with local, regional, and national political priorities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coherence with the goals of local and European political agendas, particularly with those related to migrant integration. ▪ Protocols with public administrations. ▪ Granting of public funds. ▪ Impact of good practices on the local decision-making system (public and private decision-makers' policies; allocation of local resources). ▪ Impact on the government and conditions of particularly disadvantaged contexts.

Additionally, in the framework of Work Package 5, task T5.4 "Online digital database", IMMERSE research partners collected 24 Policy Papers and 25 other tools and resources, following the methodological criteria developed for the good practices.

3 Types of good practices and resources

The present section of the report provides an analysis and graphical representation of the good practices and resources included in the database, on the basis of the main research criteria followed by the research partners for each category.

Criteria involving all the good practices and resources

- Category
- Country of origin / implementation

- Language/s in which the resource is available
- Compliance with the Dashboard Outcomes

Criteria involving the category “Good practices”

- Types of activities
- Target groups

Furthermore, key findings resulting from the comparative analysis of the 60 good practices is available in the deliverable D4.1 “Collection of good practices”.

Criteria involving the category “Policy papers”

- Target groups

Criteria involving the category “Other tools and resources”

- Types of resources

3.1 Category

Number and percentage of resources available per category

3.2 Country of origin / implementation

Most of the resources (90) have been identified in the countries of the research partners. Nevertheless, the partners have also included 19 resources identified in external countries or coming from supranational organisations.

Percentages of resources available from each country

Percentage of resources	Country of origin / implementation
-------------------------	------------------------------------

83% in total (13-15% per country)	Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain
17% in total (1-3% per country or supranational organization)	Countries: Australia, Austria, Hungary, Slovenia, Sweden, United Kingdom and United States Supranational organizations: Council of Europe, Education International, European Union, International Organization for Migration (IOM), UNHCR and UNICEF

Number of resources available from each country

3.3 Language/s in which the resource is available

The database interface is available in 7 languages: English, Spanish, Italian, French, Dutch, German and Greek. Nevertheless, the original source of the resources is available only in their respective language or languages, involving a total of 17 languages.

Almost 60% of the good practices and resources are available in English. Around 15% are available in Spanish, Italian, Greek or German, and around 9% are available in French or Dutch. Finally, 5% or less of the good practices and resources are available in other languages.

Percentage of resources which are available in the different languages

Percentage of resources	Languages in which these resources are available
57%	English

14-17%	Spanish, Italian, Greek or German
8-9%	French or Dutch
5% or less	Arabic, Bulgarian, Catalan, Czech, Lithuanian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovenian or Turkish

(Some resources are available in several languages)

Number of resources available in each language

3.4 Compliance with the Dashboard Outcomes

Each of the good practices and resources included in the database comply with several of the dashboard outcomes. This reflects the multidimensionality and complexity of socio-educational integration processes.

The following table shows three groups of dashboard outcomes and their connection with the resources included in the database. The majority of the resources (70 to 85%) comply with the first group of outcomes. More than half of the resources (51 to 61%) comply with the second group. Around a third of the resources (26 to 37%) comply with the third group.

Percentage of resources complying with the outcomes

Percentage of	Dashboard outcomes
---------------	--------------------

resources	
70-85%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children's academic skills Children's life satisfaction / happiness Children's sense of belonging Connectedness with institutions Connectedness with teachers
51-61%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to compulsory education Children complete compulsory education Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences Children remain in (formal) education beyond compulsory levels / Access to (formal) non-compulsory education Children's competence in host language Friends and peers (bridges) Friends and peers (support)
26-37%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to health care Children's legal status Types & levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended

(Most resources comply with several dashboard outcomes)

Percentage of resources with which each dashboard outcome complies

Number of resources complying with each of the dashboard outcomes

3.5 Types of activities (good practices)

The 60 good practices identified by research partners present a wide range of activities addressed to foster the socio-educational inclusion of migrant children. Furthermore, almost 80% of these good practices involve multiple types of activities. This phenomenon highlights the relevance of adopting a multidimensional approach towards inclusion.

Main types of activities

Activity	Percentage of good practices	Description of the activity
Extra-curricular activity	55%	Provide homework support, leisure and free-time activities such as sport, music, art, and dance classes
Language class	42%	Acquisition of both mother tongue and host country language skills
Vocational training	30%	Internships, youth work experiences, professional courses for teachers and school staff, mentoring and tutoring
Support	28%	Legal and school counselling, psychological support, family interventions, and actions to foster parents' participation

(Most good practices involve several types of activities)

Number of good practices matching each type of activity

3.6 Target groups (good practices)

The good practices available in the database are addressed to specific sub-groups of migrant children (newly arrived, unaccompanied, refugee and asylum seekers) involving different types of stakeholders (school principals and teachers, migrant families, educators, policy makers, etc.). Nevertheless, the great majority of good practices follow a multi-stakeholder approach addressing multiple targets.

Percentage of good practices addressed to the target groups

Percentage	Target groups
70% or more	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Newly arrived migrant children Unaccompanied and separated children
53-60%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refugee and asylum seeker children Principals, teachers Unaccompanied and separated children Migrant families, parents
45% or less	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educators, social workers Policy makers, educational authorities Other

(Most good practices address several target groups)

Number of good practices addressed to each target group

3.7 Target groups (policy papers)

The policy papers available in the database are addressed to different types of target groups. Almost 60% of these policy papers are addressed to national governments, while around one third are addressed to local entities, regional administration or international bodies, and only 4% are addressed to universities, researchers and teachers.

Percentage of policy papers addressed to the target groups

Percentage	Target groups
58%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Governments
29-38%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Entities Regional/Federal Administrations International/Supranational Bodies
4%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and CPD sites Researchers Teachers

(Some policy papers address several target groups)

Number of policy papers addressed to each target group

3.8 Types of resources (other tools and resources)

Within the category “Other tools and resources” the database provides a comprehensive set of resources focused on several topics related to the socio-educational integration of migrant children, many of them aimed at supporting teachers and migrant students in this process.

Types of resources

Type	Description of the resources
Toolkit / handbook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher's guide to help students to become familiar with the reality of migration and refuge Practical guide for frontline professionals on how to accompany a child at each stage of his/her journey Help educators to support newcomer migrant children Reception Kit for students with a migratory background Teaching and learning through play and peer education Activity kit against stereotypes and prejudices Teaching ideas to explain people's displacement
Website / e-learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support teachers in teaching literacy for migrant children Support Refugee Children and Young People Multilingual E-Learning Platform EduSkills+ Extending Teachers Competences in the effective teaching of literacy, numeracy and digital skills to refugee children Assist refugees in accessing services and exercising their fundamental rights Language as a tool of learning to activate refugee potential in society

Document / paper / article	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Migrant contributions to host and home countries ▪ Guide for educators who work with migrant and refugee children ▪ Action Plan on the integration of third country nationals ▪ Help teachers understand how stress and trauma can affect refugee children and students ▪ Need for further education provisions for migrant children in especially precarious and insecure situations,
Report / data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ COVID impact on migrant children’s existing safety nets ▪ Child participation in non-formal education ▪ Annual Report on Migration and Asylum ▪ Situation of Unaccompanied Children
Video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cultural bridge for new migrants ▪ Need for further education provisions for migrant children in especially precarious and insecure situations,
Awareness campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Raise awareness on children’s rights ▪ Raise awareness on causes for migration

Number of tools and resources for each type

4 Replicability and advancement of good practices and resources

The good practices and resources selected and included in the Online Digital Database provide a meaningful and multidimensional set of socio-educational initiatives which may support the different actors involved in the promotion of migrant and refugee children's integration in Europe. This process shall adopt a multidimensional approach matching the complexity of the socio-educational integration process through a combination of activities, multiple targets, and extended spaces of intervention. In this regard, the database represents a useful tool to capitalize this know-how, favour the transfer of knowledge and the sharing of good practices, thus promoting a common model of integration and the implementation of innovative practices in the field of education and social integration.

This section presents the set of strategies to be followed by IMMERSE partners to foster the replicability and advancement of the good practices and resources included in the Online Digital Database among the following target groups:

- Public local, regional, national and European authorities
- NGOs and other organizations working with migrant and refugee children
- Policymakers at local, regional, national and/or European level
- Civil society (especially migrant families and children)
- Schools, teachers, and education professionals
- Academic researchers in the field of migration and child education
- National and international stakeholders

4.1 Dissemination, networking and exploitation

Dissemination is a cross-cutting dimension that strategically supports the success of each aspect of IMMERSE project in terms of ensuring wide awareness, replicability and mainstreaming of the tools and results developed during the funding period, as well as their exploitation beyond this period. Activities geared toward sharing, distributing, and making use of the findings are ways to highlight the effort put forth throughout the project in order to optimize its impact.

The consortium aims to enable a larger community to take advantage of the Online Digital Database by disseminating its good practices and resources on how to promote the socio-educational integration of migrant and refugee children. The database can serve as an example and act as an inspiration for other projects in the same field as IMMERSE, scholars, and policy makers through distribution. The impact of IMMERSE is evaluated not only on the basis of the project's output quality but also based on how widely these outputs are known and utilised by parties other than the consortium. Communication and dissemination activities foreseen for the

database will help in fostering their replicability and advancement and maximizing the return on the work put into this tool by reaching a broad number of potential stakeholders.

Moreover, since the database is a relevant milestone in terms of results obtained that can be made available to the public, a combination of actions has been planned and conducted to ensure its dissemination and replicability, and reach a wide target audience (mostly macro and meso stakeholders, already mentioned above). These activities are detailed below.

Press release

As a major milestone of the project, the launch of the Online Digital Database has been communicated through a press release at European (in English) and national level in each of the languages of the project partners. The European dissemination has been made to entities, international NGOs, H2020 projects, public and private entities at supranational level. The [press release](#) is also available at the IMMERSE website.

Project's website and social media

The database is freely accessible at the project [website](#) in 7 languages. Furthermore, the database has also been disseminated through several [posts](#) at IMMERSE [social networks](#).

Newsletter

Information about the database has been included in the [news](#) section of the website, aimed at the general public, in easy-to-understand, non-specialized language, and also in the regular project [newsletter](#), which is sent to stakeholders, especially macro and meso stakeholders.

IMMERSE Hub

The [IMMERSE Hub](#), as a forum for the exchange of best practices, views and experiences, is an excellent platform to promote the replicability and advancement of the good practices and resources included in the database. To do so, various actions will be carried out until the end of the project: disseminating the database in "My feed" of the IMMERSE Conversations group, and including several good practices and resources in different languages in the different groups of "Educational resources".

Dissemination events

The IMMERSE dissemination events, to be held by October and November 2023 in 6 countries, will serve to make the project results public, committed with the open science principle, offering the knowledge and results achieved for others to use. During the events the consortium will present the results achieved, with special focus on the digital results: IMMERSE Hub, Dashboard of indicators and the Online Digital Database.

The events will be held with a hybrid format, combining the face-to-face event with online streaming. This will allow expanding the reach to a wide online audience of stakeholders at national and European levels.

European School Education Platform

Since a large part of the target audience of the database and IMMERSE in general are schools as well as teachers and educators, the European education platform has been contacted to make the database openly available to users and disseminated within this platform.

Enhance clustering and exploitation possibilities with stakeholders

Some of the dissemination actions are carried out in a centralized manner aimed at the general public and European institutions. Nevertheless, an important part of the dissemination actions, especially related to the possibilities of clustering and exploitation with relevant actors, are carried out at national level by each of the partners who know in depth their national contexts as well as the entities and organizations that can make use and exploit the good practices resources included in the database in the medium and long term.

These activities are coordinated at the project level, but each partner will carry them out freely by presenting the Online Digital Database at:

- Information sessions
- Workshops
- Face-to-face/online seminars
- Short courses
- Exhibitions or peer learning
- Meetings with stakeholders and colleagues

Data from these national dissemination and exploitation activities will be reported by the partners for follow-up at the project level.

4.2 Collaboration with schools and teachers

Schools, as main educational environments, and teachers, as main educational actors, play a significant role in the socio-educational inclusion of migrant children. In this regard, the implementation of more efficient educational models for the socio-educational inclusion should be based on a child-centred approach, where migrant and refugee children can be directly involved in the co-design and implementation of activities as key agents of their own educational and inclusion path, by means of participatory processes.

The database represents a useful tool for both schools and teachers to help them identify, adapt and take advantage of good practices and resources aimed at several complementary inclusion goals:

- Develop new school governance and management structures
- Upskill teachers and educators and provide them with practical tools and guidance materials to better manage the inclusion process
- Follow a multidimensional approach for socio-educational inclusion combining different types of activities and multiple targets
- Incorporate child-centred approaches and bottom-up participatory processes

- Collaborate with other professionals such as social workers, cultural mediators, psychologists, public authorities or other education providers
- Strengthen relationships with parents and the wider community
- Increase awareness about the challenges and opportunities of migrant children inclusion

To foster these goals, IMMERSE consortium will elaborate a proposal of collaborative workshops for schools, aimed at promoting the use of the Online Digital Database among principals, school leaders, teachers, educators and social professionals. The proposal will be aimed at explaining:

- how to use the database and take advantage of the good practices and resources included to promote inclusive education models based on child-centred approaches
- how to identify good practices and resources relevant for the school, teachers and students, on the basis of their needs and circumstances, applying a participative process
- how to co-create basic principles to evaluate if a good practice or resource is suitable to be implemented in the school

This workshops proposal will be developed on the basis of the theoretical and methodological references included in the following deliverables:

- D1.1 “Common Conceptual Framework” for inclusive education models and child-centred approaches
- D5.2 “Stakeholder Engagement Activities and Training Programme” for co-creation and participation processes

5 Annexes: list of good practices and resources

5.1 Good practices

Title	Description
Abraza África / Misión Emmanuel	<p>The Emmanuel Mission is a meeting or reception place for immigrants with a dynamic integration plan and a platform to make their reality known. The project consists of a country house where around 15 young Sub-Saharan migrants live together with the family running the project. The project has been running for 7 years, in the Municipality of Tres Cantos, in the region of Madrid. The project seeks to provide a home to young Sub-Saharan migrants where they can take responsibility for themselves, while receiving all the support they need, until becoming fully autonomous.</p> <p>“Responsible reception” involves a global attention to the person, working on the development of skills through the self-management of the project (shared house and activities), which includes the acquisition of technical skills and social abilities and practices. It also involves “Responsible education”, as young participants acquire learning compromises, attending formal education and counting on the support of volunteer teachers and mentors. Participants also get access to health care and their basic needs are met (food, cleaning, hygiene, transport). They receive an equal share of the revenues from the house garden and crafts.</p> <p>The project is funded by the Municipality Tres Cantos and private donors.</p>
ALI MSNA – 1° VOLO - Linguistic literacy and access to education - Alfabetizzazione Linguistica e accesso all'istruzione	<p>The Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR) has activated this project to favour the implementation of literacy and personalized educational paths for 1000 unaccompanied and separated migrant children (UAMs) in various schools across Italy. The aim is to facilitate their access to school and favour a rapid process of inclusion, by intervening as soon as UAMs arrive on the national territory and before their access to ordinary school.</p> <p>Linguistic literacy is facilitated using new technologies. A e-learning platform has been developed with three-level courses and various materials at disposal of teachers and students, which include also modules dedicated to the development of transversal social and civic competences, aimed at improving students' wellbeing and strengthening their relational capacities.</p> <p>The project incentivizes also other activities (art and music workshops, sports, intercultural citizenship activities, field trip, work counselling, etc.) and promotes the creation of school networks and the dissemination of good practices.</p> <p>The initiative is funded by the European Commission (Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund 2014-20) and started in 2019 with a preliminary study on the condition of unaccompanied and separated migrant children in Italy, carried out by ISMU Foundation.</p>
Barça Foundation FutbolNet program: Sports, Life Skills and Values for Unaccompanied Minors in Sicily, Italy	<p>Since 2017, UNHCR Italy and Barça Foundation have enjoyed a strategic collaboration to promote emotional and physical wellbeing and social inclusion of unaccompanied minors coming mainly from African countries, Bangladesh and Pakistan and residing in first and second reception centers in Sicily, Italy.</p> <p>Barça Foundation trains educators and social workers of the social cooperatives, Prospettiva and Il Nodo in Catania, which host first and second reception centers and provide socio-educational and recreational services to unaccompanied refugee and migrant minors. Trainings are based on two sports-based socio-educational methodologies that transmit values, life skills, and employability skills (“FutbolNet” and “FutbolNet Employability”). The trained “coaches” then deliver the program on a weekly basis with groups of unaccompanied minors, often together with Italian youth to promote integration and friendships. The program has trained 90+ coaches and included 800+ unaccompanied minors to date.</p> <p>For this program, UNHCR Italy initially liaised with Italian authorities and the reception centers. UNHCR Italy also provides ongoing advice to Barça Foundation to ensure that the program runs in line with UNHCR Italy recommended guidance, such as Listen & Learn: Participatory Assessment with Children and Adolescents.</p> <p>The project is funded by Barça Foundation, UEFA Foundation and the EU.</p>

<p>Bookcase Programme - Promoting Language and Diversity</p>	<p>The coach@school - bookcase programme (2017- ongoing) is the first multilingual reading promotion programme that links the educational locations of school/day-care centres and home. It uses multilingual books to promote the family language or language of origin in order to facilitate learning German. The multilingual, intercultural books support children in their learning development and strengthen their personality. Families are offered the opportunity to read together with their child in their language of origin, as this improves their educational opportunities and social integration.</p> <p>The main objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthening of literacy competencies and promotion of multilingualism; - Imparting of values of a tolerant society, address children's emotions and promote independent and creative engagement with the book content; - Strengthening parental involvement and promotion of educational partnerships; - Networking and cooperation. <p>Two suitcases are available for each participating school class, including twelve multilingual, intercultural, and inclusive children's books in twelve languages, a reading diary for the children and multilingual reading instructions for the parents. The books were selected based on scientific findings in anti-discrimination research.</p> <p>The project is currently implemented in Hamburg, Hamburg and Frankfurt, Hesse (expanding underway). It is funded by Foundations, NGOs, Corporations, Bildungslotterie (Education Lottery), Hamburg Funding Parliament, and Citizens.</p>
<p>Case Management Tool for Non-formal Education in Youth Work</p>	<p>The project was created because more and more children are falling out of the formal systems. The streets become the main educational environment where they develop their identity with needed attitudes and skills in order to survive. Youth work is confronted with children in different street situations. Many NGO's, citizen initiatives undertake a lot of action to connect with the children in the streets, to build trustworthy relationships. The project aimed to create a digital tool for personal case management within youth work in non-formal education. It was implemented from 01-09-2017 until 31-08-2018 in Greece, Belgium and Poland. The Coordinator of the project was the Mobile School VZW and the consortium consisted of ARSIS and PRAKSIS (Greece) and CME (Poland). In ARSIS and PRAKSIS, they work with Roma children, trafficked children in the city centre, refugee children in refugee camps and unaccompanied minors. CME works with children and youth who are working unregistered on the streets with the responsibility to sustain their families. It was a one-year Erasmus+ project granted by the European Commission.</p>
<p>Centre for Children – Frourarcheio</p>	<p>The Center for the Child is an open space for all children whose purpose is to promote and support children's rights. It is located at the Athens Solidarity Center and consists of a team of a psychologist, a project manager and an educator who directly collaborate. The space is open for all children aged from 0 to 12, with no discrimination concerning gender, origin, ethnicity, or religion (children younger than 3 years old must be accompanied by a guardian during their visit). The Center operates daily from 10:00-18:00 and the entry is free. The professional team organizes and carries out educational and recreational activities which include Greek language lessons, as well as individualized support of the children in their school subjects. Moreover, the Center organizes cultural activities and external visits in the view of a more holistic development of the child. Furthermore, the Center's psychologist provides counselling to parents, aiming to strengthen their parental role and improve the relationship with their children, as well as to children, in order to help them better manage their feelings and strengthen their self-image. The Center of the Child is funded and supported by the NGO "Solidarity Now".</p>
<p>Competence Network Democracy Education for Young People</p>	<p>The nationwide competence network is funded by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ) via the federal programme "Demokratie leben!" (Live democracy!). The official title in the federal programme is: "Competence Network - School and Out-of-School Education for Young People".</p> <p>The competence network consists of four partners which have a total of more than 100 established counselling and coordination centres at state and municipal level throughout Germany. The network thus has firmly established working relationships with over 4,000 schools, which are attended by 20 percent of pupils in Germany, and with 500 extracurricular youth education institutions in urban centres and rural areas.</p> <p>The main objective is to pool competences in order to strengthen democratic culture and structures as well as participatory approaches in school and out-of-school education for young people and to create meaningful synergies in this area.</p> <p>The project includes many activities, such as networking and knowledge transfers, publication of</p>

	<p>modules, thematic booklets, and manuals for political education, further training and counselling offers for teachers, educators and employees in schools and educational institutions, workshops and further training on various topics such as identity, interculturality, and human rights.</p>
<p>Cork Migrant Centre Youth Group Support (CMC YGP)</p>	<p>Since 2017, this project supports migrant youth in Cork who are residents of 6 Direct Provision Centres spread across Cork City and County. The CMC YGP has been developed to support the children’s educational needs; to foster confidence and develop skills that lay the foundation for engagement and integration. It consists of five key elements: homework club, dance and creative arts, girls in STEM programme, summer camps, transition year work placement.</p> <p>The project comprises a ‘safe space’ for children and youth to engage in wellbeing promoting activities and a ‘material space’ whereby the children meet. The key objective is to create an enabling environment to create opportunities for enhancing the capacities (emotional, cognitive, physical, knowledge and skills) of asylum seeking/refugee/migrant children and youth, and facilitating their social integration.</p> <p>CMC utilises a strength-based approach whereby migrant children and youth’s knowledge, skills and experience are acknowledged through participatory working methods. CMC’s programmes and activities are conceptualized within a psychosocial framework which pays attention to migrant children/youth collective risk and resilience processes.</p> <p>The project has received governmental funds from TUSLA through CYPSC, a key structure identified by Government to plan and co-ordinate services for children and young people in every county in Ireland. Funds have been also provided by Cork City Council, Community Arts office, UCC, the Glucksman, and Nano Nagle Place Company.</p>
<p>Creative Agency Programme at the Glucksman</p>	<p>Creative Agency at the Glucksman is an ongoing project to empower young asylum seekers, refugees and migrants to participate in imaginative projects that enable them to present their voices and views in the public realm. Its aim is to address isolation and marginalisation of migrant asylum-seeking children in the Cork area.</p> <p>The Glucksman is a contemporary art gallery located on the grounds of University College Cork. From the outset in 2015, the Creative Agency was conceived and delivered in partnership with the University and the Direct Provision Centres. The programme: enables young asylum seekers to work with artists and curators over an extended series of workshops; offers a positive and creative experience to a marginalized community; and provides the resources and expertise that allow the group to develop artworks for public display. Over time, children and young people develop their creative skills and expertise and see the university grounds as a safe and welcoming place for them.</p> <p>The programme is funded by Arts Council, Young Ensembles Scheme, UCC student societies, UCC Visitors Centre, Department of Justice and Equality Integration Funds (governmental funds), Fundraising activities, Glucksman’s own resources, Ireland Funds, and Philanthropic sources.</p>
<p>EGERIA PROGRAM. For the inclusion of immigrant students in intercultural schools.</p>	<p>Egeria Program addresses the issue of migrant students’ inclusion and the handling of interculturality within the educational community. The first time this program was delivered was 2006-2007 academic year. EGERIA Program is a proposal designed for all educational centers in Spain but especially offered to those centers that belong to FERE-CECA (Catholic Schools Federation) that comprises 5,939 educational centers across Spain. The general aim of the project is the inclusion of migrant students through a tool to help teachers and principals to rethink and reorder all areas and structures of the educational center to become more intercultural.</p> <p>EGERIA program is divided into four parts: a) The school in the world, which provides a theoretical framework and description of the migration phenomenon and how it is addressed at schools; (b) The world in the school, which offers a self-assessment questionnaire of intercultural education in educational communities; (c) The specific proposals of the EGERIA Program to achieve the migrant students’ inclusion within the framework of an intercultural school; d) Selection of appropriate materials, training courses, bibliography, websites, articles and proposals to give practical responses and suggestions to the objectives listed above.</p> <p>EGERIA program is funded by FERE-CECA (Catholic Schools Federation).</p>

<p>Embracing Diversity, Nurturing Integration, Learning for Life Project (EDNIP)</p>	<p>EDNIP was a research and intervention project led by the Transforming Education through Dialogue Project (TED), Curriculum Development Unit, and Mary Immaculate College (MIC) of Limerick, Ireland. EDNIP evolved through discussion with members of the PLUS and OSCAILT DEIS school networks, facilitated by TED and aimed at sharing the five participating schools' experiences of supporting migrant families.</p> <p>EDNIP developed an effective management scheme, communication strategies, and a multi-layered, holistic intervention model. EDNIP sought to promote integration through modelling effective inclusive transparent governance practices; listening to and learning from school staff, parents and children; promoting capacity building for school staff; nurturing parents and community engagement and skill development; offering a variety of in-school time, after-school and holiday opportunities; modelling effective interagency; and being informed by the literature on integration and best practice.</p> <p>EDNIP was a partnership project between MIC, the five schools, the Department of Education, Tusla Educational Support Services, Limerick City and County Council, Limerick and Clare Education and Training Board and Limerick Education Centre. EDNIP ran from 2017 to 2019. A reduced version ran in 2020/2021 and will continue to 2023. EDNIP was funded through the Asylum, Migration, Integration Fund (75%) and through TED and a Philanthropic Trust (25%).</p>
<p>Enable_Tamkin - Self-Learning for Arab Refugee Children & Building a Concept for Mother-tongue Trainers & Teachers</p>	<p>As part of the Erasmus Plus project, workshops were held with 70 Arabic-speaking tutors and trainers in Germany, Italy, Turkey, and Sweden, from 2017 to 2019. Together, a training concept and a training tool for teachers, educators and volunteers were developed to support newly immigrated children with innovative pedagogical methods, such as self-organised learning.</p> <p>Main objectives of the project were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of the concept of self-organised learning (SOL) to native-speaking mentors. - Conception of a workshop for the further training of refugee teachers. - Implementation and optimisation of the training in different European countries. - Publication of the training concept for free use by other projects in the form of interactive training modules: Basic Attitudes, Trauma, Inclusion & Exclusion, Compowerment, Motivation, Self-Concept, Self-regulated Learning. <p>The methodology was based on the design of SOL by the University of Schwäbisch Gmünd and on the user-led development of a training concept, as well as on the co-creation of workshops, including constant further improvement during the transnational workshop series.</p>
<p>FAMILIA - Famiglie Migranti: Interventi Locali di Inclusione Attiva</p>	<p>The project's main objective was to understand social unrests of migrant children and families derived from transnational migration, taking into account both internal and external factors. Furthermore, the research aimed to develop and test a complex and integrated model of taking charge: complex because it wanted to act on multiple factors, at many levels with different interventions; integrated because it wanted to bring together and coordinate all participants of the taking charge (children, parents, community, citizenship, health and social services, teachers and third sector operators).</p> <p>Through a PAR methodology (Participatory Action Research) and qualitative and quantitative methodologies, the research brought out some characteristic aspects of the onset of this unrest in children, like prolonged detachment of children from parents, economic instability, precarious housing situations, lack of parental awareness and parental tools.</p> <p>The project was implemented from 2018 to 2021 in schools, institutions, and communities (Chinese above all) in the cities of Prato and Ravenna. Academics connections with Almeria University and teachers from primary and secondary grade were established. The project received EU funds, Governmental funds, as well as financial support from third sector and local authorities.</p>
<p>Fliegen lernen – Lernwerkstatt für alle Kinder (Learning to fly - learning workshop for all children)</p>	<p>The whole program is implemented in many German regions, but the specific best practice "Fliegen lernen" has been implemented by the Catholic Primary School Zugweg in Cologne, North Rhine Westphalia. There, children from 27 nations research, discover, and learn in the learning workshop, while contributing their many languages and expand their vocabulary. The specific objectives pursued are: joy of learning, multilingual inclusive integration, science education, self-confidence, and community building.</p> <p>Since its opening in 2017, teachers have been using the learning workshop for science lessons, for instance, which are taught bilingually. Each research topic is not only developed technically, but also linguistically, not only in the teaching languages German and Italian, but also in the mother tongue of the children.</p> <p>Based on the approach of explorative learning, the children can conduct experiments, and continue them in the open all-day school workshops. In addition, kindergarten children come to the learning workshop to do research together with the primary school children, and a joint research</p>

	<p>time with parents has been established. The project is funded by the Deutsche Kinder- und Jugendstiftung (DKJS – German Children and Youth Foundation) in cooperation with Boeing.</p>
<p>FRIDA Project: Training for the prevention and detection of racism and xenophobia in the classroom</p>	<p>The project has its origin in the call of the Progress Program 2013 for the Employment and Social Solidarity of the European Commission. It was implemented from November 2014 to October 2015 and then it received additional funding for the Awareness Days in October and December 2016, and December 2017. The project was implemented in Castilla y León, Andalucía, Comunidad Valenciana and Ciudad Autónoma de Ceuta, and expression of interest was received from Castilla-La Mancha, Galicia, Comunidad de Murcia, Aragón, Comunidad de Madrid and Navarra. The general aim is to impart training for the prevention and detection of racism, xenophobia and other related forms of intolerance in the classroom, reinforcing the positive image of migrants' integration and ethnic minorities in the field of education. As well, the project aimed to comply with state provision for the Education axis "Comprehensive Strategy against racism, racial discrimination, xenophobia, and other related forms of intolerance". The methodology used was the narrative synthesis, review of pre-existing literature, and awareness campaign using stakeholders' engagement. The project was funded by EU and governmental funds: Spanish Observatory of Racism and Xenophobia (OBERAXE) and National Centre for Innovation and Educational Research (CNIIE) of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports.</p>
<p>Groep Intro vzw</p>	<p>Groep Intro is a non-profit organisation committed to working towards an inclusive society. It works across towns and cities in Flanders working on projects in the labour market, in schools, in the justice system, in communities and in leisure activities. Groep Intro engages Youth Workers who work with young people at risk of social exclusion, including those in the Secondary School OKAN classes (reception classes for foreign-speaking newcomers) both in schools and in the communities. An example of a project is CHILLweek in Mechelen aimed specifically at children from migrant backgrounds. In the Spring break of 2019, forty young people, between 12 and 18 years old from the various OKAN classes, were introduced to Mechelen leisure activities. CHILLweek was an initiative of the municipality of Mechelen, in collaboration with the Agentschap Integratie & Inburgering and Groep Intro. Groep Intro also works on projects in part-time and apprenticeship education, including dual-learning, and offers individual coaching and initial training and work experience for young people, providing access and information for accessing the local labour market. The financing comes from within. Sometimes, there are additional local subsidies to enable project extensions.</p>
<p>HE.ST.I.A. Helping Students In Acceptance</p>	<p>The project was created out of the need to build an inclusive atmosphere in the schools for all children by training teachers on how to deal with pupils having a migrant background and teach pupils the values of empathy, tolerance and acceptance towards the others. The objectives set for this project were: to provide a preparation to the partner schools in order to respond to migrant pupils inclusion, to raise awareness of the challenges faced by immigrants and refugees, and to contribute to the development of policy and good practice exchange regarding inclusion of the migrant population. It was implemented from 01-09-2017 until 31-08-2019 in Greece, the Netherlands, Belgium, Italy, Spain and Portugal. The Coordinator of the project was the 6th Primary School of Egaleo (Athens, Greece) and the consortium consisted of Maastricht Graduate School of Governance, GO! Basisschool Schaarbeek Hendrik Conscience, Istituto Comprensivo Statale "Gianni Rodari", Associação Jardim Escola João de Deus and Maristes Sants Les Corts Fundació Champagnat. It was a two-year Erasmus+ Strategic Partnerships for school education (cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices) granted by the Hellenic National Agency via the European Commission.</p>

<p>ICAM - Including Children Affected by Migration</p>	<p>The acronym CAM (Children Affected by Migration) is used when referring to children who are refugees, asylum seekers, economic or social migrants, or those left behind by family moving to another country. At the heart of the project is the concept of 'convivencia' – a Spanish word meaning 'living together in harmony' and the knowledge that children do not learn well if they are unhappy, insecure or frightened.</p> <p>The purpose of the ICAM project is to increase the inclusion and improve the learning capacity of children affected by migration by enhancing the climate of convivencia in schools and at home, by raising awareness about children's rights and the law protecting them, and by providing additional support in school and in the family for their social and emotional learning and general wellbeing. To reach this goal, the project provides for the professional development of ICAM school leaders, who will increase the capacity of schools to maintain a safe and secure learning environment and enhance Social and Emotional Learning (SEL). ICAM further integrates parent/carer education to provide additional support for families and encourage on-going SEL also in the home. The project is funded by the European Commission (EACEA) with co-funding from Erasmus+.</p>
<p>In Crescendo</p>	<p>"In crescendo" is a musical educational project promoted by the socio-educational area of the Orchestra of Castille and Leon. The intervention takes place in an educational centre situated in an urban area of Valladolid called Barrio de las Delicias, characterised by its high rate of migrant population (coming predominantly from Morocco, Romania, Dominican Republic and Bulgaria) and also by a high rate of people of Roma ethnicity.</p> <p>Starting in the first grade of primary school, instrument construction workshops are held and in the second grade students join the orchestra with which they perform live in different places. Through orchestral and choral practice children learn how to work with peers and engage in an activity that will have a final product to be performed in public. The project aims at fostering the social inclusion of students, preventing truancy, increasing motivation and self-esteem, and developing key values (respect, commitment, teamwork, patience, coexistence).</p> <p>The project first started in the primary school CEIP Allúe Morer in the schoolyear 2010-2011, where it is now part of the curriculum. Owing to its success, the project is being reproduced in five more schools. The funds are provided by Fundación SaludArte and Orquesta Sinfónica de Castilla y León.</p>
<p>In.Media.Res – Integration Mediation Responsibility (Integrazione Mediazione Responsabilità)</p>	<p>InMediaRes aims at overcoming the barriers to the socio-educational inclusion of newly arrived migrant minors with third country citizenship. The project conceives intercultural mediation as a multi-stakeholder process aimed at increasing the inclusion capabilities of the host community. Teachers, educators and public/private local actors are provided with the right tools and information to activate adequate educational and professional paths for migrant children. The methodology provides for the implementation of a model that integrates intercultural mediation, ethnopsychology, cultural anthropology, migration law and educators' experience. The goal is to create a "community of practice" through the collaboration of different actors, the creation of networks, and the sharing of good practices and knowledge. Among the actors involved, there are schools, public institutions, cultural mediators, families, educators, and children.</p> <p>The main activities include, e.g., field testing of an integrated territorial system to support non-Italian minors to access schools; trainings about psychological, ethnopsychological and cultural tools for the management of multicultural classes; creation of an online sharing point; and the implementation of a reception system with personalized educational paths for minors and support to migrant families.</p> <p>Financed with EU funds (FEI 2012), the project was implemented in Turin province during the school year 2013-14.</p>

<p>ItaStra - Scuola di Lingua italiana per Stranieri dell'Università degli Studi di Palermo – Italian Language School for Foreign Students at the University of Palermo</p>	<p>ItaStra was founded in 2008 with the aim of promoting didactic, training, counselling, and research activities in the field of Italian language teaching, through the adoption of innovative methods and people-centred models. Since 2012 agreement with Palermo Municipality, the School has started an intensive didactic and scientific activity related to the inclusion and literacy of migrant adults and unaccompanied foreign minors (UAMs). UAMs become interns and actively participate in learning spaces with refugees, asylum seekers, international students, visiting professors, European youth project participants, mobility programs professionals, etc. The didactic model focuses on the centrality of the learner and improves the non-traditional civic-linguistic skills. The School offers Italian language courses and grammar classes, as well as extra-curricular activities (cooking/photography/cinema/theatre workshops and field trips) to discover the Italian culture. Moreover, ItaStra is promoter of various projects, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studiare migrando aimed at the realization of a e-learning platform for young migrants and UAMs, who live in Italy and who are preparing the final exams of the first round of education. https://www.studiaremigrando.it/index.php/it/progetto.html - Ponti di parole: http://www.pontidiparole.com/ <p>It receives governmental funds.</p>
<p>J@M vzw Youth Work</p>	<p>J@M vzw offers educational and leisure programmes for children and young people from 6 to 15 years old. A venue and support are provided with 5 days a week during the academic year in 8 locations around the City of Mechelen, in Antwerp province. Homework help, recreational activities, projects, excursions, exam supervision, are all supported by youth workers and volunteers of the neighborhoods of the city. J@M vzw is a non-profit organization working with the local government and partners in Mechelen, Antwerp Province. The source of funding is unavailable.</p>
<p>Journeys of hope: Educational pathways to social inclusion and tolerance</p>	<p>Given that Europe is facing the greatest refugee crisis since the World War II (about 1 million refugees and migrants arrived in the EU in 2015 and Europol estimates 27% of these are children), the future school population of the EU will be increasingly characterized by multiple cultures and values. The aim of the project was to foster social integration of people with disadvantaged backgrounds, to promote intercultural dialogue, democratic values and fundamental rights, non-discrimination and active citizenship, critical thinking and media literacy.</p> <p>It was implemented from 01-09-2016 until 31-08-2018 in Greece, Italy, Spain, Turkey and Austria. The Coordinator of the project was Öffentliches Stiftsgymnasium der Benediktiner zu St. Paul (based in Austria) and the consortium was consisted of Liceo Scientifico Statale Filippo Silvestri, 4th High school of Ilion, Istanbul Lisesi and IES Joaquin Turina. The target participants were upper secondary school pupils in the ages 15–18. Working groups of approx. 16 pupils were formed in each respective school. Every 8th (alternating) pupil took part in transnational learning activities and acted as disseminators for their working group and school community. It was a two-year Erasmus+ project granted by the European Commission.</p>
<p>KAIRÓS MAJADAHONDA ASSOCIATION. Care and support for children and teenagers at risk of social exclusion, and their families</p>	<p>KAIRÓS MAJADAHONDA is an association that works with children and adolescents at risk of social exclusion and their families, in three different settings within the Community of Madrid (some reception and day-care centres in Pan Bendito and La Ventilla neighbourhoods, and “El Gallinero” Roma slum settlement in La Cañada Real). Here there is a large number of Roma population, and in recent years the proportion of the migrant population has also grown. The coexistence between the different populations often presents some challenges, with high rates of marginalization and crime.</p> <p>The general objectives of the project are: the (a) Integration of children and youth at-risk (educational, social, and labour integration); (b) Integral human promotion of children at risk of social exclusion and/or marginalization; (c) To educate children in values and enhance healthy, respectful, and committed ways of life, promoting generosity, commitment, service, and sensitivity to others’ suffering. d) Attend children at-risk, adolescents, their families in their educational and inclusive process, offering them support and presenting them life alternatives.</p> <p>The first time this project was delivered was in 1993 and is still ongoing. The project is founded by “La Caixa” Foundation and Bankia social projects, plus private donations.</p>
<p>Kinderrechteschulen NRW – Children’s Rights Schools North Rhine-Westphalia</p>	<p>The ongoing program developed in North Rhine-Westphalia by EDUCATION Y in cooperation with UNICEF puts every child as a subject and rights holder in the focus of school development. The approach focuses on Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, according to which children and adolescents are given space and encouragement for meaningful participation. The main objective is to create an inclusive, non-discriminatory, intersectional, power-critical, participatory, school- and lifeworld-based school and learning environments for all children and young people. Paradigm shift from school as a formal educational institution to a participation-</p>

	<p>oriented place of education with non-formal and informal living and learning opportunities with reference to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.</p> <p>The main activities include intra-school development including the staff of the all-day school; incorporation of the UN CRC as a part of the school curriculum; inclusion of children's rights in the school's mission statement; and local and regional networking with extracurricular partners of youth welfare services, youth associations, and local children's and youth parliaments. Overall, there are three areas of development: Organisational development, Human Resources Development, Classroom development.</p> <p>Funds are provided by NRW.Bank, UnfallkasseNRW and UNICEF Germany.</p>
<p>L'AltRoparlante: plurilinguismo e translanguaging a scuola - L'AltRoparlante: multilingualism and translanguaging at school</p>	<p>The project promotes a "translanguaging turn", which focuses on the necessity to include in the curricular educational activities all languages and dialects belonging to students' individual and collective repertoires, in the light of a multilingual learning approach. The linguistic repertoires of students are endorsed, thus improving the process of empowerment of bilingual students and de-constructing language hierarchies as well as culture-based stereotypes and prejudices, making a step beyond the sole "intercultural approach".</p> <p>The project is coordinated by the University for Foreigners of Siena (CLUSS Center) and since 2016 it has been implemented in five schools (kindergartens, primary schools and middle schools) characterized by a high presence of bilingual students and diverse linguistic repertoires.</p> <p>The main phases of the project include preliminary informative meetings with school principals, teachers, students and parents; teacher training about bilingualism and translanguaging as a pedagogical praxis; translanguaging-based activities carried out during curricular classes; data collection through different research perspectives (mostly ethnographic, interactional, cognitive ones). One of the strengths of the project is the strict interconnection between academic research and school didactics.</p> <p>The project is funded by Cassa di Risparmio di Tortona Foundation (year 2019/2020) and the CLUSS Center. Minor contributions are provided by the schools' network.</p>
<p>Learning for Integration Project: Quality Learning and Non-Formal Education for Refugees and Migrant Children</p>	<p>The aim of the project is to provide non-formal education and homework support to refugee and migrant children, as well as their parents, in order to contribute to children's smooth integration into the formal education and parents' social inclusion into the society. The NGO ELIX responded with this project to the increasing influx of refugees in Greece. The project is ongoing since 2015. Currently, the activities are being implemented in the area of Attica, in three schools of the Municipality of Athens, in Eleonas and Skaramangas refugee camps, and the Educational Center of ELIX in the city centre of Athens. In the past, ELIX had also developed actions in other locations.</p> <p>The project activities include: homework support for 6-15 year old children in coherence with formal education and remedial education through Greek and mother tongue teachers, mother tongue education, language and life-skills education for out-of-school children, early childhood education (psychosocial support, cognitive and socioemotional development and school readiness), promotion of digital learning and teachers' capacity building. The project has received funding from the DG Migration and Home Affairs of the EC, the International Organization for Migration, the Church of Sweden, Finn Church Aid, Unicef and Tides Foundation.</p>
<p>Migrant Teacher Project</p>	<p>Established in 2017, the Migrant Teacher Project aims to increase the participation of Immigrant Internationally Educated Teachers (IETs) in Irish primary and post-primary schools. Research shows that there are huge benefits to having a diverse teaching population. Migrant teachers bring a new dimension to classrooms with a diversity of perspectives and expertise that will benefit children and the education system. The project provides information, advice and training to migrant teachers who have qualified outside of Ireland, to help them to continue their profession in Ireland.</p> <p>All teachers who wish to work in publicly funded schools in Ireland must register with the Teaching Council of Ireland. The Council examines the qualifications of teachers qualified outside Ireland, and usually identifies 'shortfalls' that must be addressed prior to full registration. The Project works with these teachers to support them through the process of registration and seeking employment. The project provides a Bridging Programme for around 40 Migrant Teachers per year, facilitates a Schools Network and engages in research and advocacy work. This project is co-funded through the European Asylum Migration and Integration Fund by the Irish Department of Justice and Equality, and by the Department of Education and Skills.</p>

<p>MINT - Mentoring for Integration of third country national children affected by migration</p>	<p>Third-country nationals, including children and youth, continue to fare worse than EU citizens in terms of employment, education, and social inclusion outcomes. Migrant children and youth are especially vulnerable to social exclusion. Through the piloting of an innovative and replicable model, the MINT project aims to contribute to the successful integration of third country national (TCN) children residing in the EU, by enabling them to fulfil their full potential and lead secure, active and productive lives in the host societies, and enabling a better understanding of the intercultural benefits that interaction between newly arrived migrants and host societies bring. The project embeds a rights-based approach and promotes child participation, with specific attention to gender-based and other forms of discrimination and with the proactive involvement of the most marginalized children.</p> <p>The main instrument used throughout this project is the Mentoring guidance designed with partners and young people which foresees the implication of both children and young people coming from third countries but also children from host communities which engage and co-design individual integration projects at local and regional levels.</p> <p>The project (January 2019 – December 2020) was implemented in the Czech Republic, Poland, Romania, Slovenia and was funded by EU funds (AMIF).</p>
<p>Multitasking Cooperative Classrooms (Aulas Cooperativas Multitarea)</p>	<p>The Padre Piquer Training Centre is a state-subsidised school in Madrid, owned by the Montemadrid Foundation and run by the Society of Jesus. The project of pedagogical innovation called "Multitasking Cooperative Classrooms" was launched in the 2003-2004 academic year and continues still today, following the principles of inclusive school. The project is based on key elements: the architectural change of the classroom, a new arrangement of the curriculum, the promotion of shared teaching, flexibility in organisation, use of digital technologies and cooperative learning.</p> <p>The key objectives are cooperative learning and the possibility of carrying out different tasks in the classroom to break down barriers and then reduce school absenteeism. First, the project aims to eliminate physical barriers, turning traditional classrooms into new educational spaces that integrate about 60 students and where several teachers can work at the same time. The classrooms allow for flexible groupings, respect for different learning rhythms and cooperative interaction. Second, it erases subjects and textbooks, giving space to materials created by the teachers themselves.</p> <p>The funding sources are: Governmental funds (City Councils and in some cases regional government); Fundación Montemadrid; and since 2016, Project ACM3.0 has been financed by Bankia's initiative "En-Acción".</p>
<p>Municipal Coordination of Educational Opportunities for newly arrived immigrants as Part of the Transfer Initiative</p>	<p>The Transfer Initiative Programme Family has the overall aim of supporting and advancing better coordinated education management in districts and independent cities of Germany.</p> <p>Within the programme, one of the ongoing project is the "Municipal Coordination of Educational Opportunities for Newly Arrived Immigrants", which was launched in 2015. It focuses on supporting cities and districts in setting up a regional education management in order to offer suitable educational opportunities for all citizens in all phases of life and to make them fit for the future. The aim is to promote participation in education as the key to the social integration of new immigrants. For this purpose, 321 independent cities and districts were and are being funded. For some, the programme was the first step towards data-based municipal education management. The methodology includes mapping of landscapes, structures, and stakeholders within municipalities, interdisciplinary work and coordination, establishment of working groups, and needs assessment.</p> <p>The programme is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (and the European Social Fund of the European Union for the Transfer Agencies).</p>

<p>Netzwerk der Lehrkräfte mit Zuwanderungsgeschichte - Network of Teachers with a History of Migration</p>	<p>The Ministry of Education in cooperation with the Ministry of Integration initiated the Network of Migrant Teachers of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, which was founded in 2007 as a project with the guiding principle "More teachers with a history of migration for the schools in NRW". The main objectives were: 1. Gaining Potentials 2. Supporting Vocational Training 3. Shaping Personnel Development. The activities include: Qualification courses for teachers (such as Qualification program "Coordination of intercultural school development"), Mentoring for Student teachers, Competence seminars for (prospective) teachers in the subject area "Professional action in the migration society, Lehrkräfte Plus - A Qualification Program for Refugee Teachers, Awareness and Recruitment. In addition to the central fields of action, the network promotes the discussion of specific topics such as educational justice, digitisation, criticism of racism or even migration in the school context. The project is funded by the Government and the Friedrich Ebert Foundation.</p>
<p>NEW ABC</p>	<p>NEW ABC will deliver nine real-life pilots for the inclusion of immigrant children and youth in education that will be co-designed by the partners and the stakeholders as examples of good practices that will be tested in the nine countries involved in the project. The whole child approach will be taken into account, focusing not only on the academic needs of migrant students, but also on their social and emotional needs. This entails taking a holistic view of education and of the children's academic development, but also acknowledging the need to create formal, informal and non-formal learning environments that focus on other competences and necessities of children, their families, the community and all the stakeholders involved in the educational setting.</p>
<p>PARENTable</p>	<p>Building on the ENABLE project, the same consortium is now implementing another Erasmus+ project for the period 2019-2022. Under the name PARENTable, a workshop concept is being developed and implemented in four countries (Germany, Sweden, Italy, Turkey), that brings parents and teachers of refugee students together and empower both sides by training and mentoring. The main objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collection of best practices of great parent-teacher-understanding in Europe; - Development of an inclusive training concept for parents and teachers based on ground-experience in our five workshops in Germany, Sweden, Turkey, and Italy; - Development and provision of an e-learning course about subjects such as identities, migration and families, multilingualism, successful communication, and counselling based on the expertise of a transnational team.
<p>Parents for all</p>	<p>Europe has been for many years a major migrant destination and is becoming increasingly multicultural. Social inclusion of all newcomers and of already existing ethnic or cultural minorities (ECM) is an important issue throughout the EU. Social integration takes place at multiple levels, and one of the most sensitive fields is that of school education. An important factor affecting the integration process is parental engagement and attitude. Both parents from the host societies and migrant/refugee/ECM parents have direct influence on the attitude, behaviour and performance of their children, and consequently the integration process as a whole. The overall objective of the Parents4all project is to raise awareness, empower, and develop the intercultural competences among parents of the host societies and migrant/refugee/ ECM parents in order to enable them to contribute effectively to the social inclusion of refugee/migrant/ECM school-age children. All the work started with a need assessment and a shared intervention methodology was used in developing research tools, training materials and toolkit for self-assessment. Parents for All was a EU-funded project (KA2 Strategic Partnership for Innovation in Adult Education, 2017-2019) that ran from September 2017 to November 2019 in Greece, Italy, Spain, Germany, and Lithuania.</p>

<p>Platform Minors in Exile - Right to Education working groups</p>	<p>The Platform Minors in Exile is a national, bilingual platform of more than 55 organisations. The Platform coordinates the actions of professionals working directly with unaccompanied minors and accompanied children but who are in a precarious administrative situation or even undocumented. The Platform was created following the observation that these children cannot fully enjoy their fundamental rights due to their legal, social and administrative situation. By means of coordination, the Platform aims to improve their protection and social integration. Moreover, it aims to improve the expertise of its partners and the wider public through the animation of working groups, the conduct of research and the organisation of trainings, seminars etc. They work to raise the awareness of minors themselves about their rights. Finally, the Platform monitors the legislative and institutional framework and formulates recommendations and proposals that guarantee respect for the fundamental rights of foreign minors. Funds are provided by Brussels regional government and Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles. In the past, they have also received EU (AMIF) and private funding.</p>
<p>Progetto Su.Per. SUccesso nei PERcorsi formativi degli studenti di origine immigrata</p>	<p>The project concerned the paths of students with excellent school records despite disadvantages resulting from the difficulties of the migration experience and low socio-economic status. The project dealt with ethnic inequalities in education, seeking to go beyond a mere critical explanation of the persistence of educational disadvantage among foreign students. It consisted in a sociological study from the perspective of disadvantaged students, focusing on the ways and strategies through which they have succeeded at school. The study involved 11 higher education institutions and professional training centers in Brescia. The project was based on the collection of school autobiographies of 65 successful female and male students of immigrant origin of first and second generation, based on an extensive self-interview outline, reconstructing the past, present and future of their own and their family's school and migration experience, as well as reflecting critically on their own "school success". The project lasted from 2017 to 2019 and was promoted by Cirmib (Center for Initiatives and Research on Migration) of the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart of the Brescia office, in collaboration with the Territorial School Office of Brescia, with the financial support of the Eulo Foundation, the Catholic University and the School Office.</p>
<p>Project "INTEGRAL ATTENTION TO CHILDREN", Tomillo Foundation</p>	<p>The Tomillo Foundation is a non-profit independent entity whose purpose is to contribute to social improvement and personal development. Through the program "Integral Attention to Children", for both national and immigrant population at risk of social exclusion or in extremely vulnerable situation, it aims to assist minors and young people to achieve their social integration and autonomy, promoting the development of their personal, cognitive and socialization skills in the family, school and social contexts. They work from an integrative perspective and in coordination with the educational, social and sanitary devices of the environment. Through five axes (school reinforcement, psychological support, intervention with families, educational leisure, advocating employability), the project pretends to achieve the socio-educational inclusion of minors in order to subsequently increase their employment opportunities. In order to prevent scholar school dropout of children, the foundation proposes extra-curricular activities and supports the children and their families in their relationship. The Project is developed mainly within the city of Madrid, in the following localities: La Latina, Carabanchel, Vallecas, Villaverde, Usera, San Blas and in Majadahonda, and receives EU funds and governmental funds. It is also funded by foundations and private companies.</p>

<p>Project PERCORSI - Training, work and integration of unaccompanied minors - Formazione, lavoro e integrazione dei minori non accompagnati</p>	<p>PERCORSI is a project dedicated to the training, employment and integration of young migrants. Started in 2016, the project is operated by the Directorate General of Immigration and Integration Policies of the Italian Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and implemented in collaboration with ANPAL Servizi S.p.A. within the framework of the ESF-funded National Operational Program PON Inclusion.</p> <p>The project aims at promoting the social inclusion and job placement of unaccompanied foreign minors (UAMs) in transition towards adulthood and young migrants (up to 23 y.o.), in order to help them reach autonomy once they exit the national reception system, and counteract phenomena such as exploitation, illegal work and social exclusion.</p> <p>Two specific objectives of this project were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the implementation of 2,048 socio-occupational integration pathways using an array of individualized employment support initiatives (individual endowment). The pathways included activities such as skill assessments, job orientation sessions, and internships, as well as the creation of social support networks; - strengthening the relationship between public-sector institutional partners and key private-sector stakeholders by more accurately defining the governance structure between the groups, with the goal to formulate an integrated, sustainable, and replicable system of intervention aimed at the socio-occupational integration of UAMs.
<p>Projecte Rossinyol: Intercultural youth mentoring programme in Spain</p>	<p>The roots of the project go back to Israel in the mid-1970s, when a national tutoring programme was established for school pupils in disadvantaged situations. In the 1990s, the University of Malmö (Sweden) adapted the project to the characteristics of the city. The Näktergalen Project ("nightingale" in English) was set up in the city in 1998 to establish relationships and dialogue between university students and primary school pupils, most of them immigrants. The European Nightingale project emerged from this initiative to include universities and schools from all over Europe. The University of Girona is one of its leading members and there it is known as the "Projecte Rossinyol". Its general aim is to reduce social exclusion through the implementation of a mentoring project aimed to build one-on-one relationships between university students and adolescent pupils from different cultural backgrounds who are enrolled in schools located in areas with high rates of social exclusion. In Spain, the Rossinyol project began in 2005 at the University of Girona and is currently being carried out in different provinces of Spain such as Barcelona, Tarragona, Guipúzcoa, Navarra and Granada. The project receives economic support from City Councils and in some cases regional government or foundations.</p>
<p>Prollema: Empowering young migrants to teach their mother tongue</p>	<p>As many unaccompanied minors have been increasingly arriving to Spain, the Prollema project aims to offer language and teaching training to those young migrants who are suffering critical situations such as homelessness, unemployment and lack of access to educational opportunities. The project helps these young people prepare to become language teachers of their mother tongue after they finish the training in order to help them access the labour market.</p> <p>The project first started in 2015 and is still being implemented. Each year, four unaccompanied young migrants aged 17 to 21 who are experiencing critical situations, arrive in Barcelona and take part to a training on teaching skills and a practical workshop. Finally, they join an internship as language teachers for six months. The main objectives are to empower participants and give them a chance to develop their professional skills, fostering their participation in educational and socio-cultural settings.</p> <p>The project is funded by governmental funds (Barcelona City Council), Foundations (Biciclot, ASJTET, CAL, La Tinta, fepa, Nau Bostik, Programa UPC Reutilitza, Colectic and Minyons Escoltes i Guies de Catalunya) and fees that students pay to learn the language.</p>
<p>RAA Berlin - Regional Work Centres for Education, Integration and Democracy e.V.</p>	<p>The Network of centres carries and supports discrimination-critical participation projects in schools, educational environments and in the community in Berlin. Since 1991, it aims at the support of all stakeholders in the educational process with specific services. These include for example bilingual language-development programmes, free tutoring, school clubs, school mediation, professional training for educators, actions on parental participation with specific emphasis on families with migration backgrounds, diversity-oriented organisational development strategies, and Roma school mediation service.</p> <p>Funding and Strategic Partnership involve RAA Federal Working Group, Freudenberg Foundation, Amadeu Antonio Foundation – Initiatives for Civil Society and Democratic Culture, Hildegard Lagrenne Foundation for Education, Inclusion, and Participation of Sinti and Roma in Germany, Senate Department for Education, Youth, and Science, Senate Department for Labour, Integration, and Women, and State Office for Equal Rights - Against Discrimination, Berlin.</p>

<p>RefuEdu - Exchange of knowledge and good practice to enhance the education of refugee and sylum seeking youth</p>	<p>With the drastic rise in asylum applicants, the provision of equal educational chances remains a challenge in the educational contexts of EU Member States with young people with a migrant background being found at a particular disadvantage. The project’s objectives are to facilitate the exchange of experience and good practices in refugee education among different groups of stakeholders and among different countries, and to generate mutual learning effects in refugee education. Also, it aims to increase the stakeholders’s ability to apply functioning methods and strategies to support the education of refugee and asylum seeking youth across European countries and promote multi-stakeholder and transnational cooperation in this sector. It was implemented from 01-12-2016 until 30-11-2018 in Greece, the Netherlands, Belgium, Bulgaria, UK, Germany and Sweden. The Coordinator of the project was Stiftelsen Fryshuset (based in Sweden) and the consortium consisted of Europaisches Forum Fuer Migrationsstudien EV, University of Western Macedonia, Verikom - Verbund für interkulturelle Kommunikation und Bildung e.V., Risbo B.V., Universiteit Antwerpen, Multi Kulti Collective, Leeds Beckett University and Migration Policy Group. It was a two-year Erasmus+ project granted by the Hellenic National Agency via the European Commission.</p>
<p>Refugee Resettlement: Addressing Educational Needs of Newly Arrived Syrian and Iraqi Students in Ireland</p>	<p>This intervention was led by the NGO Doras Luimní and funded by UNHCR and the Department of Justice under the Irish Refugee Resettlement Programme (IRRP) in coordination with Limerick City Council. The aim was to address the needs of newly arrived Syrian/Iraqi migrant families across a broad range of areas of support. The intervention was executed in three geographical areas: Laois, (2015-2016), Limerick (2017-2018) and Wexford (2017-2019). Following a community development approach, the project had a wide remit in identifying holistic needs and developing appropriate interventions and learning to support the integration of newly arrived refugee families. Interventions aimed at ensuring successful access and participation in education, and bridging gaps in language competency and missed/interrupted educational pathways. Moreover, responses included attention to participants’ psycho-social needs; English language supports aimed at the particular needs of the individual children and youth; awareness raising across school staff of particular issues faced by migrant families; awareness raising among migrant communities on the Irish education framework/expectations; provision of interpreters for parents; attention to dietary needs of children at school; and financial supports for parents to meet school expenses. Additionally, separate parent integration plans to support integration into the community were developed.</p>
<p>RESTORE - Developing safer and positive school climate through restorative practices</p>	<p>The project was created out of the need to implement Restorative Practices within schools in a more sustainable way. Students and teachers work best in an environment in which they feel safe, supported and accepted. In addition, environments that have strong school climates foster the social, emotional, and academic well-being of all students. A healthy community with strong relationships is a condition sine qua non for schools that want to tackle today and tomorrow’s challenges in an innovative and sustainable way. Restorative approaches give people more voice, more choice and more responsibility, realizing a shift in the organizational culture, as demonstrated by growing evidence of positive outcomes from restorative programmes in schools, such as reduced exclusion rates and incidents of bullying, improved learning outcomes etc. The project was implemented from 01-09-2017 until 31-08-2020 in UK, France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Malta and Romania. The Coordinator of the project was Ligand (based in Belgium) and the consortium consisted of International Institute for Restorative Practices, Le Souffle, Mairie de Lille, CRESM – Centro Ricerche Economiche e Sociali per il Meridione, ASOCIATIA DE DEZVOLTARE INTERCOMUNITARA ZONA METROPOLITANA – CLUJ and Eigen Kracht Centrale. It was a three-year Erasmus+ project granted by the European Commission.</p>

<p>Rohingya Resettlement in Carlow, Ireland: Children's Integration in the Wider Community</p>	<p>The overall objective of the programme was to welcome and ensure the positive integration of 15 Rohingya refugee families in Carlow. Community integration saw the development of a range of community initiatives: sports, leadership training, women's empowerment, art projects, theatre, World Hijab Day, the drafting of a cookery book, informal network supports, and a pre-school summer camp. Community and education integration supports for children and young people were developed in order to ensure their participation, full integration across education levels and sense of belonging within the community.</p> <p>Emphasis was placed on the development of relationships of trust and belonging, and the integration of the families into the wider community, taking their level of spoken English, family support, gender, age-related and individual needs and preferences into account. A collaborative approach among all stakeholders and support services was adopted: an interagency steering group was established to co-ordinate services and a network of befrienders was created to help welcome the Rohingya families and give them assistance with day-to-day life in town.</p> <p>The project was implemented in 2008 – 2011 (UNHCR Resettlement Programme) and 2011 – Current (SICAP, Social Inclusion and Community Activation Plan, Carlow Integration Forum) in Carlow Town.</p>
<p>Rucksack Schule (School Backpack) - A Programme for Language Education and Parental Education</p>	<p>The Backpack School programme brings together the elements of multilingualism in an institutional setting based on the intercultural, diversity-conscious approach, and builds on the pillars: competence orientation, parallelisation, and cooperation within and outside the institution of school for the sustainable promotion of (real-life) multilingualism in educational success.</p> <p>Consequently, the programme combines classroom and school development with continuous language education and diversity-conscious, intercultural education involving families/parents within the framework of educational partnerships.</p> <p>The main objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consistent language education, promotion of multilingualism and strengthening of educational language competences; - Involvement of parents/families as educational partners and promotion of educational partnerships; - Migration-sensitive and diversity-conscious classroom and school development. <p>Primary school children are supported in their language development in the languages they speak. In the parallel integrated parent education, the programme increases parents' awareness of their children's learning development and strengthens them in their role as parents and their parenting skills. The parents are addressed as experts for the education of their children as well as for the learning of the family/home languages.</p> <p>The project is implemented since 2013 in North Rhine-Westphalia, and is funded by the local Ministry for Children, Family, Refugees, and Integration and the Ministry for School and Education.</p>
<p>S.U.C.RE - Supporting University Community pathways for REfugees-migrants</p>	<p>The aim of the project was to successfully build the necessary guidelines and training materials that will allow practitioners and stakeholders to facilitate the smooth integration of students and scholars in Higher Education and society. It was implemented from 01-09-2016 until 31-10-2018 in Greece, Germany and the Netherlands. The Coordinator of the project was Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the consortium was composed by the University of Cologne, VU Amsterdam and the Greek Council for Refugees. It was a two-year KA2 Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership in the field of Higher Education granted by the Hellenic National Agency via the European Commission.</p> <p>S.U.C.RE. focused on the response of the Universities to the academic needs of refugees/migrants students and scholars and to the formation of good practices guidelines through the development of training modules addressed to the voluntary sector working in the field with the specific population. S.U.C.RE. was the outcome of the Erasmus+ Programme call which had been updated to address issues around social cohesion and the integration of refugees and migrants.</p>

Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida – Almacelles	<p>Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida – Almacelles is a centre which, among its services, provides institutional foster care for unaccompanied minors aimed at their social, community and labour integration. This centre belongs to the Hospital Order of St. John of God, which is one of the largest international non-profit cooperation organizations in the world.</p> <p>Due to the strong increase in the arrivals of Unaccompanied Minors (UAMs) during the period from 2015-2018 in the Catalonia region, in April 2018, the centre opened a first Reception and Integral Care Centre to host UAMs. Here they learn the language, enter formal education and vocational trainings, to work on their autonomy and independency. In October 2018, an Emergency Protection Center was created as entry way for UAMs to the protection system. To reinforce the transition to autonomy, in May 2019 an Assisted Flat Service was then created for young people aged 16 to 18. Currently, the centre helps more than one hundred young unaccompanied migrants.</p> <p>The project is funded with governmental funds - Directorate General for Child Care (DGAIA) of the Department of Work, Social Affairs and Families (TASIF), and by the Foundation Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida.</p>
Schools of Sanctuary, Ireland	<p>Schools of Sanctuary Ireland is an initiative of Places of Sanctuary. Set up in 2016 and linked to a national UK movement, Places of Sanctuary is a network of communities across the country who come together to promote a culture of welcome to migrants and new communities seeking safety and sanctuary (communities, towns, cities, schools, higher education institutions and so on).</p> <p>The project Schools of Sanctuary is focused on extending the reach of Places of Sanctuary to school settings, involving schools and promoting their becoming proactive in developing a culture of welcome, following Places of Sanctuary principles (Learn, Act, Share). Schools of Sanctuary are schools which are committed to promoting a culture of welcome and inclusion for people seeking international protection. It aims at embedding intercultural awareness and understanding within school curricula and activities, developing intercultural skills and promoting safe and positive cross-cultural learning environments.</p> <p>The project is funded by Tony Ryan Trust, Social Inclusion Fund, Community Foundation, and AMI.</p>
SEDIN Project - Creative Methods for Successful Inclusion in Multicultural Schools	<p>The project was created because refugee children (as well as children with migrant/minority background) often face difficulties in adapting in the school environment of the host countries and the traditional cognitive models of teaching cannot cover this need. Thus, there is a need to introduce in the school environment, in cooperation with different stakeholders, alternative methods that cultivate the fantasy of the children, that promote emotional aspects of learning, positive interaction between these children and children belonging to the mainstream communities and that promote non-verbal communication and learning. The project aims to transfer two methods on this respect: Montessori Method and Creative Learning.</p> <p>It was implemented from 31-12-2017 until 28-02-2020 in Greece, Bulgaria, Belgium, Italy, Spain and Turkey. The Coordinator of the project was Action Synergy S.A. and the consortium consisted of Girona University, Karsiyaka National Education Directorate, Center for Creative Training Association, Vocational Training Center of Lesvos, Cooperazione Internazionale Sud Sud, Center of Higher Education in Theater Studies, Waterpark Montessori International, Haute Ecole Galilee. It was a two-year Erasmus+ project granted by the European Commission (Only Erasmus+ funds).</p>
Serve Now	<p>On Monday's between 19:00 - 20:30 and twice on Wednesday's (16:30 - 18:30 & 19:00 - 20:30) Serve the City, a non-profit voluntary organisation, runs a volunteer homework project and sports and recreation project called Serve Now at Leopold Asylum Seeker Centre which houses around 350 people including many children in the Brussels commune of Etterbeek. Volunteers support refugee and asylum-seeking children in different areas, including maths, language or general study. The objective is to give young people living in the centre help that is often lacking, foster community and inclusion with the host culture, and improve both physical and mental health for people who have experienced loss and sometimes trauma. It also encourages host country volunteers to engage with people living in the centres and to thereby foster understanding within the host culture. Volunteers also run games and sports activities once a week for students living in the centre. The programme is funded by donations and the workers are volunteers from across Brussels.</p>
SIREE: a cross-border project for refugees and	<p>The SIREE project aims to improve the social and economic integration of refugees by increasing their involvement in the educational process and increasing their economic independence by stimulating self-employment. In doing so, the project responds to the needs arising from the</p>

migrants	<p>recent influx of refugees in Europe. The 2 Seas region (France, the Netherlands, England and Belgium) is grappling with the challenges of integrating these families into both the educational and economic fabric. The regional school systems fail to integrate correctly the children, who are characterized by missed school years and confronted with a new education system. There is also a limited involvement of the parents and limited support for the teachers.</p> <p>The project will address the societal challenge of social exclusion by improving access to education and self-employment through the method of co-creation. In education, across the different partners, 40 new learning communities will be merged, resulting in more parental involvement in children's education, more children in school, more influx into adult education, better-trained teachers to support refugees, 50 new independent entrepreneurs and 4 new networks to support and develop entrepreneurship.</p> <p>The project is an Interreg 2 Seas programme 2014-2020 and is co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund.</p>
SIRIUS 2.0 - Project continuing the work of the SIRIUS Policy Network on Migrant Education	<p>This project continues the work of the SIRIUS Policy network which is the world's leading network doing policy advocacy on migrant education. The Network uses a theory of change approach and its model is based on network development, knowledge dissemination, policy engagement and policy reform. This part of the project lasts from September 2017 to December 2021, and involves 17 countries.</p> <p>The overall objective of SIRIUS is to feed the best evidence and practice into the major education policy debates by mobilising mainstream migration and education activities and building the capacity of migrant and grassroots education initiatives. The specific objectives are to analyse and co-create knowledge on the main challenges and policy approaches for inclusive education for children and young people with a migrant background; to identify, share and promote good policy practice and stimulate innovation and mainstreaming in policy development and implementation; and to widely disseminate results through recommendations, guidance and tools. To this end, the pan-European report "SIRIUS WATCH" is published yearly and national multi-stakeholder meetings are held. Peer learning activities are organized with local level and an international policy conference is organized every year.</p> <p>SIRIUS is funded through EU funds ERASMUS+ KA3 plus private foundation funds.</p>
Sport Against Racism Ireland (SARI) - Soccernites, Hijabs and Hat Tricks, and Diverse City	<p>SARI (Sport Against Racism Ireland) is a social enterprise, not for profit NGO that "supports cultural integration, social inclusion and cohesion in the Irish Republic, Northern Ireland and abroad by using sport as a medium to combat racism, sectarianism, xenophobia, homophobia and all other forms of discrimination in a Human Rights framework". Its projects use the medium of sport for cultural integration and social inclusion of young people of migrant backgrounds. The project Soccernites is a free-of-charge youth football and education development programme including twice weekly training and coaching for boys and girls aged 14-18. Hijabs and Hat-tricks started in early 2014 to give young Muslim women and girls the opportunity to play football. Diverse City FC is another project open to all girls and young women aged 15+. The Football Training programmes include the Football for Employability Programme and the President's Gaisce Award participation.</p> <p>The main goal is to promote the human development of boys and girls from migrant backgrounds, through educational programmes in a human rights framework.</p> <p>The projects are funded by the UEFA Foundation for Children and were once funded by Beyond Sport, Sony Mobile Young Leader programme.</p>
Stage Nederlands Voor Kinderen	<p>The municipality of Beersel in Flemish Brabant organises Dutch language courses during the holiday periods in Spring and Summer as part of an initiative to help with the integration of migrant children into the community. The courses are subsidised by the municipal authority especially for children (aged 4-12) in the Municipality of Beersel and are also available to children from neighbouring Flemish municipalities Drogenbos, Halle, Linkebeek, Sint-Genesius-Rode and Sint-Pieters-Leeuw. They are run by the non-profit organisation Hakuna Matata, and beyond the subsidised rate, a social rate for disadvantaged young people is available. The courses take place at the following vacation times: Easter holidays (5 days), Summer vacation 1 (5 days), Summer vacation 2 (5 days). Children learn Dutch in a fun way with the idea to enrich their education at the same time. They use story-telling, games and themes such as Typical Belgian, the Olympics and Time Travel. The courses are subsidised by the local authority and paid for by parents.</p>

<p>Step2School Education Programme</p>	<p>The project was created out of the need to provide remedial education in the form of afternoon support classes, which emphasizes language acquisition, mathematics, and homework support, to minors between the ages of 6-18 that live in temporary hosting facilities and are enrolled in public schools. It also accepts minors from accommodation facilities and welcomes other children that live in the neighbourhood. Additionally, intensive lessons in Greek, English and German for teenagers aged 16 to 18 are provided.</p> <p>Since June 2017, the programme is being implemented at METAdrasi’s premises and at schools in the urban area of Athens and is serving more than 2,900 students. The classes are delivered by METAdrasi’s educational staff and its objective is the establishment of a framework of support for the integration of refugee and migrant children. In 2018, the programme expanded to Thessaloniki. During the pandemic of Covid-19 the lessons take place online.</p> <p>In 2019, the programme was founded by the Hilton Humanitarian Prize and with own resources. Since summer 2020 educational programmes for refugees and migrants in Athens are also funded by Liu Kuo-Chun Educational Foundation, Hong Kong, as well as by individual volunteers’ contribution.</p>
<p>Syrische Vrijwilligers</p>	<p>The Syrische Vrijwilligers Project is a 1-year project that was co-founded by 5 volunteers with a refugee background and co-financed by the government. The idea came when the 5 volunteers got the refugee status in March 2016 and experienced the difficulties of the process when you don’t speak the language of the host country.</p> <p>The objective of the project was to help people to improve their language in order to help them to integrate, study, etc. The Syrische Vrijwilligers was based in Antwerpen, because of the high number of people with refugee and migrant backgrounds. The project involved more than 100 students in a short period.</p> <p>The project started in November 2016 and ended in November 2017 due to the lack of funding.</p>
<p>Voisins Solidaires</p>	<p>Since March 2017, La Ligue des Familles and Convivial has been offering Belgians and long-time resident citizens the opportunity to come into contact with refugees living in their immediate neighbourhood. These citizens then offer various services according to their availability, skills, desires, etc. while respecting the needs and wishes of refugees.</p> <p>Neighbours can provide help with homework or transport, discovering the neighbourhood or the city, reading mail, talking in French, sharing a meal, etc., - the type of support provided is different each time, depending on what the Belgian neighbours and refugees decide to do together.</p> <p>Convivial and the Ligue des Familles supervise the recruitment, training and networking of Voisins Solidaires between them. They also offer distance mediation and collective support throughout the project. Great freedom of action is offered to allow the relationship between Belgian neighbours and refugees to develop in a flexible and spontaneous manner.</p> <p>Since 2017, around a hundred households have met their refugee neighbours, helped them, accompanied them or simply invited them to share some time together.</p> <p>The project is funded by La Ligue des Familles and Convivial.</p>
<p>Waterford Integration Services - Engagements in Education</p>	<p>Waterford Integration Services (WIS) is an NGO providing since 2006 a range of support services to refugees, asylum seekers and migrants in the South-East region of Ireland. WIS’s Access and Equity Framework ensures that they are responsive to the needs of culturally and linguistically diverse communities, supporting them in participating as full members of society.</p> <p>Education Interventions include work with the Roma community, Asylum Seekers and Refugees. Among the initiatives there are: advocacy services, outreach and remote supports, education training and employment, youth programmes. WIS especially advocates for the engagement of women and girls in education and promotes a human rights-based approach to all programmes underpinning the principles of non-discrimination, equality and inclusion, consultation and partnership building.</p> <p>WIS works with agencies such as the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission, Migrant Rights Centre of Ireland, International Organisation for Migration, European and Irish Networks Against Racism, Local Authorities, Government Departments, An Garda Síochána, Foreign Embassies and localised service providers to address the statutory obligations that Ireland has signed up to under the United Nations international human rights treaties.</p> <p>Projects are financed with governmental and Local Authority funds, SICAP, and IHREC.</p>

5.2 Policy papers

Title	Description
CEPS: Migration integration policies at the local level in Belgium	<p>This policy paper focuses on labour market integration of new arrivals into Belgium. Migrant children's lower educational attainment levels are taken as symptomatic of a serious integration problem. Individual local actors and networks (initiatives, organisations, and other stakeholders) are identified, contextualising child migrants' civic and economic integration within broader migration issues. This paper emphasises the need for greater communication and coordination, as well as more targeted policies from Belgian governance structures.</p>
Department of Education and Skills and the Office of the Minister for Integration (2010) Intercultural Education Strategy 2010-2015.	<p>This Intercultural Education Strategy ("IES") aims to ensure that: All students experience an education that "respects the diversity of values, beliefs, languages and traditions in Irish society and is conducted in a spirit of partnership" (Education Act, 1998). All education providers are assisted with ensuring that inclusion and integration within an intercultural learning environment become the norm. The IES was developed in recognition of the recent significant demographic changes in Irish society, which are reflected in the education system. The Strategy builds on existing work in this area and seeks to be of relevance for all sectors of education, in line with the high level goal of the Department of Education and Skills ("DES") to "support and improve the quality, relevance and inclusiveness of education for every learner in our schools".</p>
Department of Justice and Equality (2017) Migrant Integration Strategy: A blueprint for the future.	<p>The Migrant Integration Strategy was developed as the Government's response to the challenge of promoting integration in a context of increased diversity in Ireland. Its vision is to enable migrants to participate on an equal basis with those of Irish heritage. Its primary objective is to ensure that barriers to full participation in Irish society by migrants or their Irish-born children are identified and addressed. The Strategy is intended to work towards the long-term vision in which integration is embedded in communities, workplaces and broader society. It proposes a number of targeted initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to increase migrant participation in specific areas (such as in entrepreneurship or public sector employment); • to address particular migrant needs (such as in education and health); and • to address challenges (such as on data gaps). <p>In relation to migrant children the Strategy envisions that migrant children will be supported to benefit fully from the education system. Actions will include integration issues will be mainstreamed in the work of all appropriate Government Departments and agencies and addressed in their Strategy Statements, Annual Reports and other documents.</p>
Discussion Paper Multilingualism North Rhine-Westphalia. Approaches and suggestions for the further development of linguistic and cultural diversity in schools. Ministry for School and Further Education of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia	<p>The discussion paper now presented lists many approaches to linking instruction in German, foreign languages and other subjects as well as instruction in the language of origin. At the same time, it formulates the perspective of a multilingualism that will be lived in schools and society as a matter of course in the future, in which an increasing number of children and young people will speak at least a second language in addition to German. This is a longer-term development process to be designed with academia, schools, non-school partners, and institutions responsible for teacher education and training. The position paper covers the following points:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multilingualism as an educational goal in North Rhine-Westphalia 2. Multilingualism in the institution school 3. School development 5. Didactics of Multilingualism 6. Long-term strategy

Education (Admission to Schools) Act 2018	The Act is intended to create a more parent-friendly, equitable and consistent approach to how school admissions policies operates for all primary and post primary schools. This should help to ensure that all children, regardless of nationality or religion, should be able to access education. For example provisions include the requirement for schools to set out arrangements for students that do not wish to attend religious instruction. This is particularly important in Ireland as the majority of state funded primary schools have a Catholic Ethos. These changes will encourage a more inclusive environment in Irish education. The Act also give the Minister of Education power to compel schools to open special classes.
Effects of the 'Corona Crisis' on Migrant Children and their Integration	This policy brief intends to evaluate the consequences of school lockdown due to Covid-19, and to propose new ways of stimulating the sustainable integration of migrant pupils in the future by making policy recommendations to different local, regional and national bodies. It takes into account the possible effects of national measures to contain the Corona pandemic on the integration of migrant children, in light of insights from the project Migrant Children and Communities in a Transforming Europe (MiCREATE). The global Corona (COVID-19) pandemic has changed 'normality' and everyday life. The measures taken by national governments all over Europe in order to contain it particularly affect vulnerable groups, such as migrant children. The lockdown of schools and the measures enforcing social isolation might have a negative and lasting impact on the well-being of these groups of children and might deepen the existing inequalities they are already suffering.
ELIAMEP: The integration of refugees in educational system in Greece: Policy and management in "moving sand"	The Ministry of Education in 2016 implemented a plan for the integration of children up to 15 years old in the national educational system and the creative employment of children in infancy and pre-infancy in the accommodation structures. This program was implemented in two stages. In the summer of 2016, artistic activities were organized in the refugee reception centres. Secondly, during the school year 2016-2017, afternoon classes started every day in the country's schools for four hours in Greek, English, mathematics, arts, and more, intending to integrate refugee children into the educational system. Be that as it may, during the first year of this program, many weaknesses were depicted. Firstly, a significant weakness identified was the teachers' lack of preparation; thus, they were incapable of catering effectively to the needs of the refugee students. Additionally, another weak spot was the absence of any plan for the involvement of parents in the educational process due to the lack of interpreters in the Refugee Accommodation Centre and schools. However, the most severe problem that hinders the integration of refugee children in schools and Greek society is the resistance and reactions of the local community.
Global Framework for Refugee Education: Refugee Inclusion into pledges for concrete action to help achieve inclusive and equitable quality education for all by 2030.	This Framework aims to create the conditions for global support for the education of refugees and host communities to meet the commitments of the Global Compact on Refugees and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particular SDG4, which aims to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all' by 2030.
Human Rights at the Southern Border 2019: Migrant Children	This policy paper intends to analyse the situation of migrant children, the state of their rights and guarantees from their arrival in Andalusia until they become adults. The aim of this report is to denounce the systematic violations that are taking place, contrary to international, national and regional regulations which establish "the best interests of the child" as a guiding principle that should guide all policies, decisions and actions. It also makes visible APDHA's (Andalusian Pro Human Rights Association) proposals and demands in order to achieve a comprehensive model of child protection that addresses the specific circumstances of children who migrate without the company of adults in the recognition of their rights and the development of their life projects.

<p>Intercultural and digital citizenship paths with second-generation youth: the #IOPARTECIPO project, in the Tuscany region.</p>	<p>The #IOPARTECIPO project aimed at improving the active participation of migrants, focusing on the target group of the “second-generation” youth (2G), implementing the proposals contained in the 2G Manifesto promoted by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies. In particular, the project used training and participatory tools to enhance the young 2G residents in Tuscany to encourage their participation in the economic and social context in which they live. To this end, innovative training and participation systems have been used which have also benefited from new technologies and in particular the potential of Open Toscana platform.</p>
<p>IOM: Migrant and displaced children in the age of COVID-19: how the pandemic is impacting them and what can we do to help</p>	<p>The COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped how we approach security and movement. In places where ‘social distancing and washing hands with soap and water are not an option’, such as migrant facilities in low- and middle-income countries, the pandemic has had a particularly harsh effect. This policy brief details the impact of COVID-19 on four dimensions of risk in child migrants’ lives internationally: poverty, survival and health, education, and protection and safety. Legal shifts due to COVID-19 are also identified. Recommendations include providing accurate, up-to-date pandemic information; halting refoulement, deportation and detention; and implementing education strategies for migrant and displaced children.</p>
<p>Mainstreaming 2.0. How Europe Education Systems can Boost Migrants Education.</p>	<p>This report explores the progress made towards the long-term goal of ensuring that European education systems are attuned to diversity. Its starting point is that adapting the full spectrum of education systems to diversity must be part of a broader, societal project that both re-evaluates existing processes and systems and reshapes the role of educational institutions as integration actors.</p>
<p>Position paper on migrant and refugee children from SOS Children’s Villages International</p>	<p>SOS Children’s Villages is one of the most well-known NGO’s advocates children’s rights. Children are affected by migration in at least three ways: they move with their family; they migrate alone, without their parents or legal guardians; or they are left behind by migrant parents who have no other option than going abroad to secure the means of subsistence for their family. In all these cases, children face specific challenges to the rights to special protection and care. Thus, policy and program responses to the movement of refugees and migrants must include provisions that grant children the continuum of care and access to relevant support services. International law recommends protecting the children, granting safe, regular channels for migrants and refugees, enhancing any cooperation between governmental and non-governmental actors, ending immigration detention of children and their caregivers, and ensuring these children’s human rights and basic needs. It also recommends protecting every child’s right to quality care, identifying, tracking, and monitoring refugee and migrant children through disaggregated data and assessing special vulnerability, investing in capacity building of professionals, investing in sustainable development, and fostering the participation of migrant and refugee children and young people. The NGOs above have taken place on special occasions are Mexico, Western Balkan Route, Austria, and Finland, providing care and protection responses for migrant and refugee children.</p>
<p>Position paper on the relevance of inclusion in schools and its effect on education and on lack of school attendance in Italian schools.</p>	<p>Nowadays School is called to face a complex challenge: not only to teach students didactic units but also to include and support children and adolescents in becoming citizens aware of their rights; moreover, to assume the responsibility to respect, protect and promote the rights of other people. Save the Children’s report analyses data and facts on Italian schools by formulating recommendations to combat early school leaving and to increase well-being at school, giving voice to students and teachers.</p>
<p>Programme for the integration of the refugee children into public education, implemented by the Hellenic Ministry of Education</p>	<p>Since September 2016, the Hellenic Ministry of Education has implemented a program to integrate refugee children into public education. The purpose is the ambiguous relations that have been developed since then between the Ministry and the non-governmental organizations active in the field of refugee education. As a result, the program examined relations between the Ministry and the International Organizations (IOs) and NGOs. There is also an attempt to explain the conditions under which these relations are shaped. Their main features are complementarity and competition, more or less. The reasons for the competition are different at the central macro-level and the micro-level, meaning staff relations between the Ministry and NGOs. It’s worth mentioning that there is a downward effect, in the sense that the attitudes and behaviours of individuals are directly affected by the stance adopted centrally by an organization towards the Ministry of Education and its</p>

	<p>policy. Moreover, the paper details the program for the education of refugees, along with comparative data for the two years 2016-2018. Disputes with international organizations and large international NGOs are also examined, which ultimately serve the same objectives as government agencies.</p>
<p>Recommendations from the Roundtable "Child Protection & European Funding for mobile populations in Greece: Report and prospects for the future "</p>	<p>On 16 May 2021, a Roundtable organized by a group of NGO's (NGO Advocacy working group): ActionAid, Danish Refugee Council, Defence for Children International Greek forum for refugees, International Rescue Committee, Solidarity Now, Terre des Hommes Hellas, Network for Children's rights, with the support of EPIM and Initiative for Children in Migration. The roundtable's goal was to discuss the issues of the reception system and the perspectives of integration of refugee and migrant children in Greece in the light of European funding. In the spotlight of the discussion were the refugee crisis of 2015 and the struggles and chronic inefficiencies of the Greek system of reception, asylum, including child protection. Among the critical challenges, unaccompanied children face the correct registration of their data by the authorities, the timely arrangement of legal guardianship, the proper accommodation. The roundtable urges the Hellenic Government and the EU to collaborate on a standard policy to protect and promote unaccompanied children's rights in the future.</p>
<p>School meets unaccompanied minors: actors, duties, and rights that come into play.</p>	<p>This guide reconstructs the process of reception of unaccompanied minors in Italy, identifying the jurisdiction of each actor involved and highlighting the importance of their collaboration to achieve a successful integration and inclusion of these children/teenagers. School is not the only institution in charge of this task but there is a multitude of actors involved: the social services of local authorities, the courts for minors, the host communities, the voluntary guardians, and of course third sector organizations that are part of the local welfare system.</p>
<p>Teacher Education in the Immigration Society. Equipping for the Normal Practice of Diversity. Policy Brief of the SVR (Expert Council of German Foundations for Integration and Migration) Research Unit and the Mercator Institute for Language Support and German as a Second Language, funded by Foundation Mercator: 2016-4.</p>	<p>Despite the political commitment of the federal states, the reality of working in multilingual and culturally diverse classrooms continues to play only a secondary role in teacher education and training. This policy brief argues for improved, robust, and transparent teacher education on all levels in all federal states of Germany.</p>
<p>The protection of migrant and refugee children in Spain and Europe</p>	<p>In the document Save The Children examine five key issues: protection at Europe's external borders; detention of migrants and refugees; access to asylum and residence; family reunification and guardianship of minors. The report aims to highlight the most important changes affecting the lives of children, based on a general assessment of the situation in Europe and with a specific focus on specific measures taken in Spain.</p>
<p>The rights of unaccompanied and separated children at Spain's southern border.</p>	<p>The purpose of the report seeks to offer a comprehensive view of the situation of migrant children arriving at Spain's southern border, to analyse the main policies and practices that are being implemented, and to identify the barriers they face in exercising their fundamental rights, with a particular focus on accompanied and separated children.</p>

<p>UN report: The Voice of Migrant and Refugee Children Living in Belgium</p>	<p>This brief exposes a series of interviews of 170 migrant children performed by UNICEF. They detail their experiences with education, housing policies, and emotional wellbeing in their home and host countries, as well as their journey. Salient points include the loss of protection brought by familiar structures such as family, as well as insecurity due to housing and legal procedures. The brief then provides policy recommendations; firstly, children's policy recommendations (an invaluable look within the Belgian asylum and integration procedures) and finally UNICEF's recommendations based on the data collected. Children's recommendations include clear procedure instructions, ending age tests, tailoring their education to their needs (smaller classes, more contact with Belgian children) and favouring family reunification. UNICEF recommendations include an end to children's detention, family unification and a clear commitment to centering children's voices in the process.</p>
<p>UNHCR: Reinforcing the protection of unaccompanied and separated children in Belgium</p>	<p>This report provides an in-depth exploration of current trajectories for unaccompanied migrant children in Belgium, exposing their shortcomings and offering recommendations accordingly. These include information and recommendations on registration, identification and age tests (e.g. Abolish detention, fair use of age tests, information available to children with language adapted for them); tutoring and mentoring (e.g. Immediate provision of a mentor, equalising mentor quality); forms of care and availability of services (e.g. Availability of a variety of welcome structures, continuity up to and past the age of 18, psychology and mental health services); legal procedures in children's interest; and child participation. Durable solutions and their possible undertaking are identified, providing judicial context, assessing the need for systems that aid young people; and incorporating the careful intersection in public perception of 'child' and 'migrant'. 51 recommendations are offered.</p>
<p>Vulnerable groups in the asylum system. An approach to the needs of children, LGTBI+ persons and victims of trafficking</p>	<p>The purpose of the report is to give a voice to particularly vulnerable people in the asylum system, namely children, LGTBI+ persons and victims of trafficking, in order to better understand the conditions that ensure a more adequate and quality assessment of asylum applications, as well as the specific reception needs of refugee children, LGTBI+ persons and victims of trafficking.</p>
<p>Young Refugees in the Education System. Challenges for Schools, Policymakers, and Administrators. Flight, Research, and Transfer Project by the Institute for Migration Research and Intercultural Studies and the Bonn International Center for Conversion Policy Brief 08a.</p>	<p>This brief presents recommended actions on the basis of an overview article on the state of the art of research "Refuge and Education" on access to education, interlinking of formal and non-formal education, systematic and strategic orientation on the resources of refugees, sustainable development through continued education strategies, attention to young people as a special target group, and consideration of regional characteristics and rural areas.</p>

5.3 Other tools and resources

Title	Description
Beyond borders: a pedagogical proposal on migration and refugee issues	<p>This document is a teacher's guide to help students in all age ranges (5-18) to become familiar with the reality of migration and refuge through a series of activities that will allow them to empathise with the different situations that people experience as part of the migration crisis. One of the core objectives of this guide is to contribute to build a citizenship compromised with social justice and that is competent in order to live together in a democratic way with people from different cultural origins. In this sense, intercultural education is seen as a key tool to achieve this goal, as it allows to build positive cultural relationships and bonds between different groups of people aimed at creating fairer societies. Fostering empathy, cooperation, respect towards diversity and the necessary skills to live together is imperative to achieve this. This guide offers a series of activities and group dynamics oriented towards participation and focused on the students. It offers flexible and adaptable activities and it encourages the participation of the whole school community (teaching body, student body and families).</p>
Caritas: A common home: migration and development in Belgium	<p>This paper provides an in-depth historical analysis of migration in Belgium, data on migration flows (as of 2019), and details migrants' many contributions to their host and home countries. It also emphasises obstacles to these contributions, such as lack of safe and legal pathways, infringement of basic needs, access to labour markets, access to nationality, public opinion and political discourse. It offers an understanding of past and present migration policies and their role in guiding migrants towards a fruitful future. Contradictory and inadequate policies are described and explained, with proposed modifications when relevant.</p>
Curing the Limbo Project, from the city of Athens	<p>The Municipality of Athens, in collaboration with the Kapodistrian University of Athens (UoA), the Catholic Relief Services (CRS), the International Rescue Committee (IRC), and the Development and Tourism Promotion Company of the Municipality of Athens (EATA) co-created and ran the pilot program "Curing the Limbo" (2018-2021). The program was based on the methodology of action research which had a dual function: On the one hand, the activation of the refugee potential in Greek society and on the other hand, the creation of a multifaceted background that would only be beneficial for the refugees. In addition, it developed project-based learning that aimed to facilitate the connection of language courses with activities in Athens and contained the teaching of two languages, Greek and English. The language was used as a tool of learning. The entire learning process was focused on the "how" and not on the "what" that will be taught. The participants were recognized refugees who lived either in open accommodation facilities or in apartments in the center of Athens. The above project adopted three pedagogical approaches:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The pedagogy of literacy 2. The pedagogy of intercultural awareness 3. The pedagogy of place-based education
DASPA, a cultural 'bridging' class	<p>This video functions as, firstly, a partial interview and secondly a look into the DASPA system. DASPA classes function as a cultural bridge for new migrants: they are a French intensive language course within certain schools in Belgium geared towards cultural integration. This video interviews DASPA students, gives an insight into DASPA classes and life after the DASPA program.</p>

<p>EC Action Plan on the integration of third country nationals</p>	<p>The Action Plan on Integration provides a common policy framework For EU Member States as they further develop and strengthen their national integration policies for migrants from third countries, and describes EC the policy, operational and financial supports available to support these actions. In relation on education the action plan makes a number of specific recommendations for member states:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide online language assessment and learning for newly arrived third country nationals, especially refugees, through the Erasmus+ online linguistic support. • Support peer learning events on key policy measures such as welcome classes, skills and language assessment, support for unaccompanied children, intercultural awareness, recognition of academic qualifications and integration into higher education. • Support the school community in promoting inclusive education and addressing specific needs of migrant learners through the COM online platform School Education Gateway. • Remove barriers to the participation of third country national girls and boys to early childhood education through the development of the European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC), including assistance to ECEC staff to respond to the specific situation of families. • Equip teachers and school staff with the skills needed to manage diversity and promote the recruitment of teachers with a migrant background. • Promote and support the participation of migrants' children in early childhood education and care.
<p>Economic and Social Research Institute (2021) ANNUAL REPORT ON MIGRATION AND ASYLUM 2019: IRELAND, European Migration Network.</p>	<p>The Annual Report on Migration and Asylum 2019: Ireland provides an overview of trends, policy developments and significant debates in the area of migration and international protection during 2019 in Ireland. It was written by the ESRI who are the Irish National Contact Point of the European Migration Network. The aim of the European Migration Network (EMN) is to provide up-to-date, objective, reliable and comparable information on migration and asylum at Member State and EU levels with a view to supporting policymaking and informing the general public and the Annual Report on Migration and Asylum is a key part of this work. The purpose of the EMN report is to provide an insight into the most significant political and legislative (including EU) developments at State level, as well as public debates, in the area of migration and asylum. Net inward migration for non-EU nationals to Ireland at April 2020 is estimated at 19,000. The International Protection Office (IPO) received 4,781 applications for international protection in 2019, an increase of 30.2 per cent from the 3,673 applications in 2018. Ireland's applications accounted for 0.64 per cent of the total 745,255 applications made in the EU-28 countries in 2019. A total of 42 suspected victims of trafficking were identified during 2019.</p>
<p>E-Learning: Supporting Refugee Children and Young People</p>	<p>In this course, teachers have the opportunity to learn how to support children in dealing with the consequences of chronic stress, violence and insecurity in everyday school life. So that young refugees can feel a little safer at school, recover, and learn again despite stressful life circumstances. The course consists of different parts, which can be completed flexibly and separately from each other. In total, the course includes teaching material for 4 hours. The courses are a cooperation project between the Dutch Augeo Foundation, the Federal Association of Unaccompanied Minor Refugees, and the Federal Association of Psychosocial Centers for Refugees and Victims of Torture.</p>
<p>Erasmus + Project - HOPEFUL-Extending Teachers Competences in the effective teaching of literacy, numeracy and digital skills to refugee children - Webinar June 2021, launching of online material for teachers, toolkit / e-learning</p>	<p>HOPEFUL is a European initiative with the main purpose of enhancing teachers' competences in the teaching of numeracy, literacy and digital skills to refugee and migrant students so as to promote their successful integration in education and improve their school performance. Additionally, throughout HOPEFUL an innovative diagnostic tool will be developed in order to effectively assess the gaps and needs of migrant as well as refugee's children in aforementioned sectors. Primary goal of HOPEFUL is to encourage students to continue their education despite the difficulties they face when integrating into the national educational system. Furthermore, HOPEFUL aims to promote innovative practices in teaching literacy, numeracy and digital competences to refugee and migrant children with interrupted education. Moreover, HOPEFUL will succeed its goals through four pillars: the identification of the necessary skills of secondary school teachers in order to cater for the needs of migrant and refugee children. Secondly, a capacity building program will be designed for teachers and school teachers. The third and fourth pillar are not only to develop a diagnostic tool for evaluating the gaps and needs of secondary school migrant and refugee children but also an online platform where teachers can hone their skills through digital modules.</p>

Eurochild: Growing up in Lockdown: Europe's Children in the age of COVID-19: Belgium Country Profile	This country profile offers data on COVID 19's impact on migrant children's existing safety nets, specifically children in CiAC (alternative care). Tackling child poverty and children's participation are recommended, and details on progress of these key elements are given.
How to convey child-friendly information to children in migration. A handbook for frontline professionals	This handbook is a practical guide for frontline professionals on how to accompany a child at each stage of his or her journey: from arrival at our borders to finding durable solutions towards integrating into the host country. The handbook offers food for thought and practical applications to encourage professionals to think critically about how they communicate with children and to encourage the respect of their rights, including the right to be heard and to participate in the procedures affecting them. This practical handbook for professionals working with children affected by migration or otherwise on the move has been prepared by the Council of Europe Children's Rights Division in the context of the Council of Europe Strategy for the Rights of the Child (2016-2021) and the Council of Europe Action Plan on Protecting Refugee and Migrant Children (2017-2019).
Human Rights Watch: A Step Forward for 10,000 Rohingya children: Bangladesh allows kids to receive formal education / 'Are we not human?': Denial of education for Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh	Nearly 400,000 Rohingya refugee children in Bangladesh aren't getting a formal education. This article and video detail a pilot study approved in January 2020 to teach 10,000 children the Myanmar curriculum at unofficial schools set up by Rohingya refugee teachers. This article and adjacent report emphasise the need for further education provisions for migrant children in especially precarious and insecure situations, and the need for education to become accredited. It details the minutia of current plans regarding Rohingya children's education and the obstacles posed by the Bangladeshi government
Kit SottoSopra: Activities and dialogues against stereotypes and prejudices	Activity kit against stereotypes and prejudices. All the activities were conceived by the boys and girls of the Save the Children SottoSopra Movement, with the aim of creating spaces for dialogue and discussion at school, among students and between students and teachers, about stereotypes and discrimination within our society.
Multilingual E-Learning Platform EduSkills+	The multilingual platform EduSkills+ is dedicated to different cosmopolitan education strategies and their growing importance in the European and international context. The website offers diverse, engaging and motivating materials for teachers to help children and young people understand the challenges of our diverse society and to help them reject radical worldviews. The platform and all materials are available in English, German, Italian, Polish, Slovak and Slovene. It includes three main elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ready-to-use modules tackling diversity and global issues as well as for implementing philosophical inquiry in classrooms; • Multilingual media library with a collection of resources, materials and model projects from different countries; • Online video tutorials for teachers on how to use and implement the materials. Teachers can access a wealth of materials for a total of 77 school hours.
Professional Development Service for Teacher: Team-Teaching for Literacy	Professional Development Service for Teacher: Team-Teaching for Literacy seminars rolled out nationally and provides guidance to Special Education and mainstream class teachers in how children for whom English is an additional language can be supported in their own classrooms through the inclusive team-teaching model. The website contains webinars and resources such as team teaching resources as the 2019 guide 'Effective Interventions for Struggling Readers' to support teachers in teaching literacy for all children. The website also contains useful educational resources for teaching English as an Additional Language and a guidelines in facilitating inclusion in mainstream classrooms.

<p>Promoting integration of migrants and refugees in and through education. Toolkit</p>	<p>This document is a guide developed by Education international (EI) for educators and education unions who work with migrant and refugee children. It compiles strategies and practical actions in a new toolkit by Education International (EI). The aim of the publication is to give practitioners concrete, hands-on recommendations and advice that will help them contribute to making education more inclusive and an effective right for all children.</p>
<p>Reception Kit for students with a migratory background</p>	<p>This kit aims at helping teachers and education professionals in the reception and inclusion process of students with a migratory background. Different forms are proposed, in order to track the level of inclusion and integration of the student (both socially and linguistically) and his/her specific situation, picturing its evolution through time.</p>
<p>Refugee.Info in Greece</p>	<p>Refugee.Info is a team from around Europe, Middle East, South Asia, Africa, and America. It is a non-profit online platform that works with partners, United Nations agencies, NGOs, governments, refugees, and asylum seekers. The primary purpose of the Refugee.Info project is to assist refugees in Greece in accessing services and exercising their fundamental rights. More specifically, it provides the most up-to-date and helpful information on a range of community issues, such as asylum procedures, work permits, school enrollment, and even finding a doctor. All the information is available in many languages: English, Arabic, Farsi, French, Urdu, Lingala, Somali, and Kurmanji. Moreover, Refugee.Info provides technical information for other categories as well. Due to the measures taken against COVID-19, many services have been temporarily suspended. However, the platform is constantly updated according to the latest developments on the issue. Finally, information is provided for women, health insurance, unaccompanied children, financial assistance, transportation, finding a job, and housing.</p>
<p>Reports & data published by UNICEF & EKKA (National Center of Social Solidarity), regarding the unaccompanied children in Greece</p>	<p>EKKA is a specified national service under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. With the support from UNICEF, publishes a bi-weekly updated report on the situation of Unaccompanied Children in Greece based on accommodation referrals sent to the Service for the Management for Accommodation Requests of Unaccompanied Minors. The data is available online. At the same time, EKKA offers Social Care services such as a hot-line service for unaccompanied children and Shelters for women and children victims of exploitation, trafficking, and abuse. It has also developed a Coordination and Management Service for the housing requests of unaccompanied asylum seekers. Moreover, EKKA has developed coordinating activities such as creating National Registers for the monitoring and evaluation of activities of social care and solidarity for vulnerable groups. Also, the Child Protection Operational Co-ordination Service for the interconnection of service providers, a Certification Service for NGO's that offer social care services, the publication of reports, Centers of Life-long learning for the training of professionals, and the Service of European co-funded projects that develops projects on social protection, awareness and battling social exclusion. Finally the Center, contracts agreements with state actors, local authorities, and Volunteer Organizations on the issue of emergency assistance to vulnerable groups.</p>
<p>Roads to refuge: Teaching ideas to explain people's displacement</p>	<p>Teaching ideas, activities, and lesson plans about refugees for teachers and education professionals. The page is divided into 4 sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is a refugee? • Refugee journeys • Refugee settlement • Refugees in Australia <p>Each section provides different lessons.</p>
<p>Teaching and learning through play_Peer education</p>	<p>Through a peer education path, the students of two high schools have attended a training course on crucial issues such as inequalities and social inclusion and then used these bases to imagine activities and games suitable for children aged between 6 and 12 years. Each laboratory was built according to the methods of active and participatory teaching, based on involvement and first-person experience, on play and cooperative learning.</p>

<p>U.S. Department of Education (Department) Newcomer Tool Kit (2016)</p>	<p>The tool kit is designed to help educators to support newcomer migrant children including Refugee and Asylum Seeking children. The key objectives of the toolkit are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand and strengthen opportunities for cultural and linguistic integration and education. • Support educators to understand some basics about their legal obligations to newcomers. • Provide welcoming schools and classrooms for newcomers and their families. • Provide newcomers with the academic support to attain English language proficiency (if needed) and to meet college- and career-readiness standards. • Support and develop newcomers' social emotional skills. <p>The Newcomer Tool Kit provides (1) discussion of topics relevant to understanding, supporting, and engaging newcomer students and their families; (2) tools, strategies, and examples of classroom and schoolwide practices in action, along with chapter-specific professional learning activities for use in staff meetings or professional learning communities; and (3) selected resources for further information and assistance, most of which are available online at no cost. The toolkit provides very practical supports and lesson plans for teachers and educators.</p>
<p>Understanding child participation. Ideas, strategies and dynamics to work on child participation step by step.</p>	<p>This document collects dynamics, strategies and above all good ideas to work and understand something as important as child participation in non-formal education. The report includes promotion and dissemination of children's rights, promoting and energizing child participation.</p>
<p>UNHCR: Teaching About Refugees - Guidance on Working with Refugee Children Struggling with Stress and Trauma.</p>	<p>This document aims to help teachers understand how stress and trauma can affect refugee children and students, and also to give some tips and advice to teachers on how to successfully include children and students who suffer from stress and trauma in their classrooms.</p>
<p>UNICEF: Children uprooted</p>	<p>Children uprooted – a UNICEF campaign centred around children living in Ireland who are refugees and migrants. This educational campaign has lessons for primary and secondary students to raise awareness and knowledge of children's rights and the specific experiences of children who have been uprooted from their homes, families and cultures through video and classroom discussion.</p> <p>Classroom workshops have been devised for primary and secondary school to prompt these conversations. They are in line with relevant curricula and rather than adding to teacher's workloads, are intended to be taught in an integrated manner. The workshops have been tested in classrooms and reflect the input from teachers and pupils.</p> <p>The aim of the programme is for all children to have positive shifts in values and attitudes towards diversity and solidarity with refugees and migrants. Students will learn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify the rights of children • To identify root causes of the global, local and personal understanding of displacement • To identify their own cultural lens and how it impacts on relating to others • To increase their activism in support of refugee and migrant children
<p>Why People flee. Causes of Flight and Migration - A topic for Education and Society. Medico International & GEW (German Education Union))</p>	<p>This brochure encourages people to listen carefully when talking about the causes of flight and the combating of them, and to take into account real facts.</p>